

GreenDIGIT

Greener Future Digital Research Infrastructures

Deliverable D3.2 Environmental Impact Assessment Methodology and Guidelines for RIs

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4.3, 4.5	The impact assessment scope, including the RI system boundaries and environmental impact dimensions, were updated to include Scope 3 emissions emerging from supply chain impact and RI stakeholders.
5	Metrics for environmental impact assessment were updated to encompass embodied carbon, specifically for the Global Warming Potential (GWP).
6.1, 6.2, 6.3	The impact assessment steps were updated to make 'stakeholder engagement' and 'governance and compliance' categories mandatory components to answer in the self-assessment questionnaire. These are now required for the full completion of the impact assessment to encompass assessment relating to procurement and external stakeholders.
8.6	The guidelines for termination were updated to include impacts in context of Scope 3 emissions.

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Executive Summary

Reducing the environmental impact of digital services and technologies must be a priority both in the operation of existing services and in the design of future digital infrastructures. This deliverable presents the development of an environmental impact assessment methodology and guidelines for digital Research Infrastructures (RIs) resulting from the GreenDIGIT project.

The GreenDIGIT impact assessment methodology aims to assess the impact magnitude of RI practices related to carbon emissions, energy consumption, waste management, and water use across their lifecycle. The deliverable proposes a set of metrics and indicators, which RIs can use to assess their impact for these categories, including Global Warming Potential (GWP), Cumulative Energy Demand (CED), Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), and Resource Depletion: Water (RDW).

The methodology provides a framework to define improvement and implementation priorities to help RIs address the most critical impacts as a priority and to implement actions in a resource-effective manner. To do so, the methodology provides three parameters to guide the assessment: impact magnitude, likelihood, and effort required.

The methodology is complemented by a self-assessment questionnaire (reported in GreenDIGIT Deliverable D8.1), which offers a practical tool to complete the assessment steps and answer detailed questions on the capability level of each topic area. The methodology provides a theoretical base for the assessment, and the questionnaire offers a practical tool to implement it. They have been developed as a joint service for RIs to assess their overall environmental sustainability ex ante and formalise an action plan to monitor and report on progress ex post.

The RI assessment has been tested and validated by the participating RIs of GreenDIGIT (EGI, EBRAINS, SoBigData, SLICES) with reports on the use cases outlined in the deliverable, offering customised environmental reports with recommended actions tailored to their assessment levels.

The deliverable also offers a set of general practical guidelines intended to support RIs at each stage of the lifecycle from concept development to termination. These guidelines can be used either with the RI assessment or independently by providing in-depth recommendations that RIs can use for establishing best practices.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AWARE	Available Water Remaining
CC	Climate Change
CED	Cumulative Energy Demand
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
CUE	Carbon Usage Effectiveness
EE	Energy Efficiency
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EoL	End-of-Life
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESG	Environmental, Social, Governance
ESRS	European Sustainability Reporting Standards
EU	European Union
EU DC CoC	European Code of Conduct for Data Centres
GB	Gigabyte
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GreenDIGIT	Greener Future Digital Research Infrastructures (current project)
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HW	Hardware
FU	Functional Unit
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Lifecycle Assessment
LCIA	Lifecycle Impact Assessment
PRACE	Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe
PUE	Power Usage Effectiveness
PV	Photovoltaic
RAM	Random Access Memory
RDW	Resource Depletion: Water
RI	Research Infrastructure
SAQ	Self-Assessment Questionnaire
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UN	United Nations

WEEE	Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment
WP	Work Package
WUE	Water Usage Effectiveness

1 Introduction

The GreenDIGIT project aims to develop comprehensive strategies and tools to assess and reduce the environmental impacts of digital Research Infrastructures (RIs) across Europe. This includes developing and validating a consistent framework with innovative technical solutions, models, and tools to increase the environmental sustainability of digital RIs by lowering their impacts throughout the whole lifecycle.

This deliverable, **D3.2 “Environmental Impact Assessment Methodology and Guidelines”**, reports on efforts from Work Package 3 on tasks T3.2 “Environmental Impact Assessment Methodology for Research Infrastructures” and T3.3 “Guidelines and best practices for reducing environmental impact and energy consumption”. It introduces the GreenDIGIT environmental impact assessment methodology, along with corresponding sustainability metrics, guidelines and best practices, targeted for DIGIT infrastructures within the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) roadmap and other digital service providers.

The environmental impact assessment methodology provides a framework to assess the impact magnitude of RI practices with respect to activities related to carbon emissions, energy consumption, waste management, and water use across the RI lifecycle. The methodology is aligned with relevant industry standards and adapted to diverse local contexts of RIs. It draws from the findings of the Deliverable **D3.1 “Landscape review, best practices analysis and identification of needs within the ESFRI RIs”** [1] and incorporates insights from surveys conducted across RI communities.

The environmental impact assessment methodology is complemented by the self-assessment questionnaire, reported in **D8.1** [2], which provides a practical tool to implement the steps of the methodology. The assessment is validated through its application with four participating RIs (EGI, SLICES, SoBigData, and EBRAINS) and reported with use cases. These initial assessments serve as a foundation for future project outputs, including the development of a greenRI certification for sustainable practices in the DIGIT domain.

The practical guidelines and overview of best practices support the RI assessment by providing detailed recommendations for each step of the lifecycle (as defined by the ESFRI lifecycle approach) to help RIs move toward sustainable approaches.

1.1 Objectives and purpose

The core purpose of this deliverable is to present a **robust environmental impact assessment methodology and guidelines** that enable Research Infrastructures (RIs) to evaluate and address their environmental impacts across several areas, including carbon emissions, energy, water, and waste generation, and identify opportunities for impact mitigation and improvement.

The deliverable is firmly rooted in the **objectives of Work Package 3**, which include developing a detailed understanding of the environmental sustainability practices of the participating RIs, assessing the broader ESFRI-related digital service provider landscape, conducting desk research to identify state-of-the-art and adoptable solutions for monitoring environmental impacts, and defining a comprehensive set of metrics through which environmental performance can be consistently assessed and monitored.

The deliverable contributes directly to **Objective 1 (O1)** of the GreenDIGIT project: assessing the status and trends of low-impact computing within four participating digital Research Infrastructures (EGI, SLICES, SoBigData, and EBRAINS), as well as within the broader digital service provider community of ESFRIs. In support of the verification of O1, this deliverable produces customised environmental impact reports for the four participating RIs, providing insights into their environmental footprints. Furthermore, it formulates strategic recommendations tailored to the specific contexts of these infrastructures, with the aim of guiding future actions to reduce environmental impact and to support the development of sustainable digital research ecosystems.

2 Deliverable methodological approach

The environmental impact assessment methodology presented in this deliverable is developed by drawing upon and integrating four existing established frameworks. These frameworks have been used as guiding principles to ensure that the methodology is both comprehensive and aligned with relevant standards and policy developments. The frameworks contribute conceptually and structurally to the overall assessment approach, which have been used and adapted to serve the operational and strategic realities of digital Research Infrastructures (RIs).

2.1 ESFRI Lifecycle approach

At the foundation of the GreenDIGIT methodology is the ESFRI Lifecycle Approach, a model developed by ESFRI to guide the planning and evaluation of RIs. The ESFRI lifecycle includes distinct phases (concept development, design, preparation, implementation, operation, and termination) each with its own strategic and operational characteristics. Within this framework, the methodology and guidelines in this deliverable identify specific points at which environmental considerations should be addressed.

Using the ESFRI lifecycle as a guiding structure enables the GreenDIGIT methodology to embed environmental impact assessment across the full timeline of an RI's development and use. This approach supports the integration of sustainability from the earliest planning stages and allows for consistent environmental performance tracking over time. This is particularly important for alignment with the ESFRI Roadmap 2026, which calls for RIs to demonstrate sustainable practices, and align with the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS), which require structured and transparent environmental disclosures.

By aligning with the ESFRI lifecycle, the methodology ensures it can be operationalised within the specific context of ESFRI Thematic Infrastructures, and it can better address the specific needs and constraints of RIs depending on their state of progress in the lifecycle. It also enables benchmarking across different RIs and contributing to the development of common practices in the DIGIT domain.

2.2 Lifecycle Assessment methodology

The methodology is further grounded in the Lifecycle Assessment (LCA) approach as standardised in ISO 14040, which analyses the entire lifecycle of a product, considering which resources are extracted from the environment and which harmful impacts or inputs are returned to the environment. It spans from extraction of raw materials, manufacturing, and transportation, to utilisation, and eventually disposing or returning to the cycle through recycling or repurposing.

Within the GreenDIGIT methodology outlined in this deliverable, we identify and use relevant environmental impact categories and indicators in line with LCA principles. The use of standardised impact categories enhances the transparency and comparability of results for decision-making and reporting.

2.3 IAM4SDG methodology

The IAM4SDG methodology has been developed from the NAIADES project funded under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme as a structured framework to assess how actions contribute to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Within GreenDIGIT, this framework provides a useful foundation for shaping the structure of the environmental impact assessment methodology. IAM4SDG supports the definition of key parameters, such as impact magnitude, effort required, and prioritisation, which are essential for comparing potential environmental actions and strategies. By incorporating this structured logic, the GreenDIGIT methodology enables RIs to evaluate the relative significance and feasibility of different measures, ensuring that the assessment outcomes directly inform practical and impactful sustainability planning.

2.4 Environmental, Social, Governance (ESG) methodology

The Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) framework provides a high-level lens for evaluating the organisational and strategic context in which environmental decisions are made. In the GreenDIGIT methodology, ESG serves as a complementary perspective that connects technical impact assessments with governance structures, institutional policies, and stakeholder accountability.

The environmental dimension of ESG is particularly relevant in framing the assessment outputs as actionable, strategic recommendations. It also supports integration with the ESRS, which are becoming increasingly relevant for RIs in terms of public accountability and alignment with EU climate and digital transition goals. Incorporating ESG thinking ensures that the methodology can not only guide technical evaluation, but also inform institutional practices and long-term sustainability planning.

3 Review of relevant standards

This section presents an overview of key international and regional standards relevant to the environmental impact assessment and sustainability management of digital RIs. The standards reviewed here provide essential frameworks, best practices, and compliance requirements that have informed the development of the GreenDIGIT methodology and guidelines. Following an initial broad survey of applicable standards, a curated selection of the most relevant standards is identified to guide and align the project’s assessment approach with established industry norms and regulatory expectations.

3.1 International standards

Table 1: Review of relevant international standards for environmental impact assessment methodology.

ISO Environmental Management Systems	
ISO 14001:2015	Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use
ISO 14001:2015/Amd 1:2024	Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use Amendment 1: Climate action changes
ISO 14002-1:2019	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for using ISO 14001 to address environmental aspects and conditions within an environmental topic area-Part 1: General
ISO 14002-2:2023	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for using ISO 14001 to address environmental aspects and conditions within an environmental topic area-Part 2: Water
ISO 14004:2016	Environmental management systems — General guidelines on implementation
ISO 14005:2019	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for a flexible approach to phased implementation
ISO 14006:2020	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for incorporating eco-design
ISO 14007:2019	Environmental management — Guidelines for determining environmental costs and benefits
ISO 14008:2019	Monetary valuation of environmental impacts and related environmental aspects
ISO 14009:2020	Environmental management systems — Guidelines for incorporating material circulation in design and development
ISO 14040:2006	Environmental Impact Assessment – Principles and Frameworks ISO 14040:2006 provides a structured and systematic approach to conducting Lifecycle Assessments, helping organisations assess and improve the environmental performance of their products, processes, or services. Involves: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lifecycle Assessment • Goal and Scope Definition • Lifecycle Inventory Analysis (LCI) • Lifecycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) • Interpretation
ISO 14044:2006	Environmental Management – Lifecycle assessment – Requirements and guidelines
ISO 14051/52 and 53	Material flow cost accounting
ISO Energy Management Systems	
ISO/IEC 30134 standards group	Information technology – Data centres key performance indicators. Where Part 2: Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) Part 8: Carbon Usage Effectiveness (CUE)

	Part 9: Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE)
ISO 50001:2018	Energy management systems — Requirements with guidance for use
ISO 50002-1:2025	Energy Audits – Part 1: General requirements with guidance for use
ISO 50004:2020 (More standards available)	Energy management systems — Guidance for the implementation, maintenance and improvement of an ISO 50001 energy management system
International Telecommunication Union- ITU-T L.: 1300-L.1399 Series	
ITU-T L.1300	Best Practices for Green Data Centres
ITU-T L.1301	Measurement Methodologies for Data Centre Energy Management
ITU-T L.1302	Assessment of Energy Efficiency and KPIs in Data Centres
ITU-T L.1310	Guidelines for Green ICT Services
ITU-T L.1316	Energy Efficiency Framework
ITU-T L.1320	Energy Efficiency for Telecommunication Equipment
ITU-T L.1330	Guidelines for the Use of Renewable Energy in ICT
ITU-T L.1332	Total network infrastructure energy efficiency metrics
ITU-T L.1333	Carbon data intensity for network energy performance monitoring
ITU-T L.1381	Smart energy solutions for data centres
ITU-T L.1410	Methodologies for assessing the environmental impact of ICT goods, networks, and services
ITU-T Y.3021	Guidelines for energy efficiency in data networks and network devices
Greenhouse Gases Includes requirements for the design, development, management, reporting and verification of an organisation's GHG inventory.	
ISO 14064-1:2018	Greenhouse gases - Part 1: Specification with guidance at the organisation level for quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions and removals.
ISO 14067:2018	Greenhouse gases - Carbon footprint of products - Requirements and guidelines for quantification. Provides a standardised methodology for assessing the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with each stage of the product's lifecycle.
EC TR 62921	Quantification methodology for greenhouse gas emissions for computers and monitors.
GHG Protocol (Greenhouse Gas Protocol) ICT sector supplement	Standards and Guidelines: For measuring and managing emissions from operations, supply chains, and products. Corporate Standard: Framework for companies to measure and report GHG emissions. Project Protocol: Guidelines for quantifying reductions from GHG mitigation projects.
Environmental Management - Water Footprint Provides principles, requirements and guidelines for conducting and reporting a water footprint assessment as a stand-alone assessment, or as part of a more comprehensive environmental assessment.	
ISO 14046:2014	Environmental management — Water footprint — Principles, requirements and guidelines
ISO/TR 14073:2017	Environmental management — Water footprint — Illustrative examples on how to apply ISO 14046

3.2 Regional standards and frameworks

Table 2: Review of relevant regional standards for environmental impact assessment methodology.

European Code of Conduct for Data Centres (EU DC CoC)

EU DC CoC - Voluntary initiative launched by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC)	<p>The EU DC CoC aims to promote energy-efficient design and operation of data centres and to encourage the adoption of best practices to reduce energy consumption. It provides benchmarks for energy performance. The Code of Conduct best practices include [3]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management Practices: Developing an energy efficiency strategy, monitoring energy use, and setting energy performance goals. • IT Equipment: Utilising energy-efficient servers, storage, and network equipment; consolidating and virtualising IT resources. • Cooling: Implementing efficient cooling systems, using free cooling where possible, optimising airflow management, and increasing operating temperatures within safe limits. • Power Equipment: Enhancing the efficiency of power supply units, uninterruptible power supplies (UPS), and power distribution. • Building and Infrastructure: Designing and maintaining energy-efficient building infrastructure, including lighting and environmental controls. • Monitoring and Measurement: Regularly measuring and monitoring energy usage to identify opportunities for improvement.
EU Delegated Regulation (EU) 2024/1364	
EU Delegated Regulation (EU) 2024/1364	EU Delegated Regulation (EU) 2024/1364 of 14 March 2024 on the first phase of the establishment of a common Union rating scheme for data centres.
EN 50600 series	
EN 50600	The EN 50600 series is a set of European standards that provides a framework for the planning, design, construction, operation, and sustainability management of data centre facilities. Developed by the European standardisation body CENELEC, it aims to ensure consistent performance in terms of availability, physical security, energy efficiency, and environmental sustainability. [4]
Directives on Waste Management	
EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC)	The EU's Waste Framework Directive lays down basic waste management principles, including recovery and recycling, and is legally binding for all EU Member States.
RoHS-Restriction of Hazardous Substances (2002/95/EC)	The RoHS, adopted by the EU and legally binding for all EU Member States, sets out restrictions for the use of specific hazardous materials found in electrical and electronic products.
WEEE Directive (2012/19/EU)	The Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) Directive aims to prevent, reduce, and manage the waste produced by electrical and electronic equipment. The WEEE Directive provides a framework for the collection, recycling, and recovery of such waste, promoting environmentally sound management practices.
Directive on Renewable Energy	
EU Renewable Energy Directive (2023/2413)	The Renewable Energy Directive sets binding targets for the use of renewable energy in the EU's overall energy mix and establishes measures to promote its deployment.

3.3 Selection of most relevant standards and frameworks

To identify the most pertinent standards for the GreenDIGIT environmental impact assessment and guidelines, a survey was circulated among consortium partners to gather overall insights and practical perspectives. This activity was closely linked to Task T10.3, which focuses on initial standardisation and policy liaison efforts, ensuring alignment between the project's outputs and broader regulatory and industry frameworks. The selected standards and frameworks reflect those deemed most relevant and applicable to the digital RI context within GreenDIGIT and the needs of the environmental impact

assessment and guidelines. These standards and frameworks were actively consulted and served as a reference throughout the development of the methodology and guidelines, ensuring that the process was both robust and well-aligned with established best practices.

Table 3: Selection of most relevant standards and frameworks.

ISO 14001:2015	Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use
ISO 50001	Energy management systems — Requirements with guidance for use
ISO/IEC 30134-1:2016	Information technology — Data centres — Key performance indicators
EN 50600	The European Standard for Data Centres
ITU-T L.1410	Methodologies for assessing the environmental impact of ICT goods, networks, and services
ITU-T L.1300	Best Practices for Green Data Centres
ITU-T L.1301	Measurement Methodologies for Data Centre Energy Management
ESRS	European Sustainability Reporting Standards
WEEE Directive (2012/19/EU)	Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) Directive

4 Assessment methodology purpose, requirements and focus

4.1 Assessment methodology purpose

The environmental impact assessment methodology is designed to provide a structured approach for evaluating environmental practices and guiding mitigating efforts. Its main purposes are to:

- **Identify and assess RI environmental practices and corresponding impacts;**
- **Rank impacts** in two categories: **impact magnitude & likelihood;**
- **Identify recommended mitigating actions;**
- **Rank mitigating actions** in terms of **effort required;**
- **Classify impacts and mitigating actions** in two categories of priorities: **improvement priority & implementation priority;**
- **Monitor impact** over time;
- **Monitor mitigation actions' implementation** over time;
- **Report on evolution and progress;**
- **Provide a framework which can be developed to certify** the effective and continuous environmental sustainability actions.

4.2 Assessment methodology requirements

To ensure consistency, robustness, and applicability across different contexts, the environmental impact assessment methodology has been designed to meet the following requirements:

- **Comparable across different sites and sizes:** same indicator value in different contexts should indicate same level of impact;
- **Comparable over time;**
- **Simple to understand and easily measurable;**
- Based on **international unit systems;**
- **Representative of dimension** to be measured;
- **Reliable;**
- **Meaningful:** assess categories that represent a large part of the total environmental impact;
- **Relevant for ESFRI roadmap 2026 and ESRS.**

4.3 RI lifecycle and system boundaries

The GreenDIGIT impact assessment methodology enables the evaluation of cross-cutting RI lifecycle phases to provide a comprehensive environmental impact assessment. The lifecycle assessment phases follow the ESFRI lifecycle approach, as defined for the ESFRI Roadmap, see figure 1, which is taken from the ESFRI Roadmap 2026 [\[5\]](#).

Figure 1: ESFRI RI lifecycle approach [5].

To ensure valuable and comparable assessments, the methodology focuses on measurable impacts directly related to or indirectly associated with the RI's activities. The assessment includes environmental impacts under the RI's operational control as well as other significant indirect impacts across the value chain, including embodied carbon.

In order to collect and report on accurate data, primary quantitative inventory reporting is highly encouraged. However, secondary data or reliable estimates may be used when data are limited, provided that assumptions and data gaps are transparently documented.

The operational lifecycle stage accounts for the majority of the direct environmental impacts. However, substantial indirect impacts also arise across the other lifecycle stages. This is particularly relevant to account for embodied carbon in raw material acquisition, production, and end-of-life (EoL) treatment [6] and across supply chain and stakeholder impacts.

In order to account for the embodied carbon in Scope 3 emissions, RIs need to consider the total of their purchased goods and services, capital goods, fuel- and energy-related activities, upstream transportation and distribution, waste from operations, business travel, and employee commuting [7]. For RIs and data centres, major embodied carbon comes from infrastructure and server lifecycles, which can represent a substantial amount of the overall carbon footprint.

Accurate quantification of Scope 3 emissions and embodied carbon remains challenging due to the complexity of hardware supply chains and variability in equipment specifications. However, approximation models have been developed to support estimation. The Open Compute Project Foundation and iMASONs taxonomy for carbon disclosure [8] provides a structured framework for reporting embodied impacts across server and infrastructure lifecycles.

Recommendations for engaging stakeholders in sustainable practices are also included in Section 9 guidelines of this deliverable and provided as a dedicated category in the GreenDIGIT Deliverable **D8.1** Self-Assessment Questionnaire [2], where the impact assessment is conducted.

See figure 2 for an overview of the lifecycle scope definition for the assessment methodology in this deliverable. The presented lifecycle model is compatible with the RI Lifecycle Model described in Deliverable **D4.2** [9] and Whitepaper on RI Lifecycle Model [10].

Figure 2: RI lifecycle scope definition: Assessment methodology.

4.4 RI components

The following RI components should be considered as part of the inventory for data gathering and impact reporting in the environmental impact assessment methodology, particularly for RIs in the operation phase. This forms a general overview, which needs to be adapted to each RI's specific requirements and set-up when using the methodology.

- (1) Physical infrastructure and data centres comprising computation, storage, network, and IoT/sensor devices;
- (2) Scientific applications carrying out scientific workflows and data processing;
- (3) Data and data management infrastructure guaranteeing data storage, access, and sharing.

A functional unit (FU) for measurement of impacts from the RI components should be assigned by the RI for the purpose of data gathering and impact reporting in the impact assessment methodology. FU is a quantified description of the performance of the product systems, for use as a reference unit, i.e. 1 TB of data storage over 1 year, 400 GB of RAM per second. In order to assess broader impacts of an entire lifecycle phase, it may be useful to employ a functional unit to capture the total impacts in a given time frame, i.e. total RI energy consumption per year (MJ), total e-waste generated per hardware lifecycle (kg of WEEE, kg recycled waste).

4.5 Environmental impact dimensions

Environmental impact categories are used in an LCA framework to classify and quantify the impacts or inputs that are returned to the environment across the lifecycle of a product. ISO declares that the selected impact categories need to reflect a comprehensive set of environmental issues based on the and goal of the product or system under assessment [11].

The ITU-T L. 1410 adapts ISO's LCA framework specifically for the scope of ICT goods, networks, and services. It states that although multiple impact categories are needed to comprehensively evaluate the environmental impact of a product, the only mandatory category is climate change, also referred to as global warming potential (GWP) in various standards. For this category, the most recent global warming characterisation factors from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change should be used for each GHG with a timeframe of 100 years. For other impact categories, there is no methodological consensus in the LCA community [6].

Multiple impact categories could be considered for the assessment of digital RIs. Please see Annex A for a list of examples of impact categories and indicators, as outlined in ITU-T L.1410. The GreenDIGIT impact assessment methodology for RIs considers a set of analysed flows or impact categories for cross-cutting phases of the lifecycle. As outlined in figure 2, the impact assessment in this deliverable analyses the flows of CO₂ emissions, energy, waste, and water across the RI lifecycle to form an overarching assessment of their impacts. To match this scope, we have defined four main impact categories: **Global Warming Potential (GWP)**, **Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)**, **Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE)**, and **Resource Depletion: Water (RDW)**. The climate change category considers all CO₂ emissions resulting from Scope 1, direct emissions from sources owned or controlled by the RI; from Scope 2, indirect emissions from the consumption of purchased electricity and other flows; and Scope 3, indirect emissions from activities that the RI is indirectly responsible for across the value chain. The cumulative energy demand category considers the amount of primary energy consumed throughout the lifecycle stages. The waste category assesses the total amount of waste disposed, including waste of electrical and electronic equipment, and the amount of waste recycled or repurposed. And finally, the resource depletion of water is considered in terms of total water use and effectiveness.

Based upon the results from the GreenDIGIT survey reported in Deliverable **D3.1** [1], most RIs that were surveyed did not report on eutrophication, acidification, toxicity, or land use as significant environmental variables in their activities. The environmental impact assessment methodology will therefore focus on the top four categories, GWP, CED, WEEE, and RDW introduced above to be assessed throughout the RI lifecycle scope.

Please see table 4 for an overview of the identified impact indicators to measure each impact category. These reflect mid-point indicators that allow us to determine comparable results across different RIs with impacts from their operations. We will not include the scope of end-point categories or indicators in this impact assessment methodology, i.e. species extinction, diseases, or quality of life, as they do not allow for comparable direct causation measurements from most RIs.

Table 4: Environmental impact categories.

Environmental impact category	Environmental impact indicators
Global Warming Potential (GWP) / Climate Change (CC)	Kg CO ₂ eq
Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)	Megajoules [MJ] of primary energy demand

Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE)	Total electrical and electronic waste (kg)
Resource depletion: Water (RDW)	Total water use (l)*

* While total water use (l) gives a first overview into the water category, this alone does not account for overall depletion impact where a given region's water availability would need to be accounted for. Section 5 delves into this topic and use of water in the GreenDIGIT methodology further.

5 Metrics for environmental impact assessment methodology

This section proposes a set of practical metrics and associated calculation methodologies to support environmental impact assessments for digital RIs. These metrics aim to guide RIs to better understand, track, and reduce their environmental impacts, integrated into the environmental impact assessment methodology to assess their usage and effectiveness.

The approach recognises the diversity of infrastructures in scale, technical configuration, and data availability. The suggested metrics are selected based on the methodology requirements laid out in section 4.2, including comparability across different sites and timeframes, representativeness of dimensions, reliability, and ability to capture meaningful environmental performance across the previously identified four environmental impact categories:

1. Climate Change / Global Warming Potential (GWP)
2. Energy Consumption / Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)
3. Waste / Waste from Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE)
4. Resource Depletion – Water Use (RDW)

The inclusion of metrics supports the overall methodology framework to assess any given RI’s stage of environmental activities and impact, and to help identify recommended actions to mitigate negative impacts and leverage opportunities. The assessment encourages RIs to use available data, such as utility bills, monitoring dashboards, system documentation, procurement records, etc. to develop an initial environmental baseline, and to identify opportunities to further integrate environmental metrics into their operational monitoring and management where lacking.

Each impact category below includes relevant indicators and calculations, allowing RIs to build environmental awareness and identify areas for improvement. While the first three categories measured in terms of CO₂ emissions, energy, and waste are highly relevant for all RIs, the final category of water may be more or less relevant to different RIs depending on the region and climate they are based in and the level of water availability in their area. In a classical LCA, the total amount of water consumption should be calculated in context to its local impact, i.e. how much water is depleted. Lifecycle Impact Assessment methods, like AWARE (Available WATER REmaining) could be used to develop impact factors (i.e. water deprivation per region) that convert water use into RDW impact units, such as ‘m³ water-equivalents’ or ‘m³ deprived’ [12]. While standard LCIA methodologies offer detailed modelling of water scarcity and regional depletion, these methods require granular, location-specific data and advanced modelling capacity. Heterogeneity of RIs presents challenges in applying a uniform RDW impact method in a meaningful and comparable way across sites. In the GreenDIGIT methodology and self-assessment questionnaire [2], we propose the use of Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE) as a pragmatic water performance indicator, which enables consistent tracking of how effectively water is used relative to the output or service delivered by the RI (e.g., per experiment).

Table 5: Metrics for the environmental impact assessment methodology.

CO₂ emissions	Global Warming Potential (GWP)	$GWP = Operational\ emissions \times Embodied\ emissions$
Energy	Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)	$CED = \sum(Operational\ energy\ in\ MJ) + \sum(Embodied\ energy\ from\ production, maintenance, EoL)$

	Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE)	$PUE = \frac{\text{Total facility power}}{\text{IT equipment power}}$
Waste	Total waste of electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE)	$\text{Total WEEE (kg)} = \sum(\text{Mass of each discarded device (kg)} \times \text{Quantity discarded})$
Water	Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE)	$WUE = \frac{\text{Litres of water use}}{\text{kWh of equipment energy use}}$

5.1 Global Warming Potential (GWP)

Indicator: Kg CO₂-equivalent (CO₂-eq)

Metrics: Total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are expressed in CO₂-equivalents using standard GWP factors. In calculating GWP over a 100-year timeframe, carbon dioxide (CO₂) is used as a reference gas whereby its GWP is set to 1 by definition [6]. Other greenhouse gases, including methane and nitrous oxide, are measured relative to CO₂ equivalents.

In the context of the RI environmental impact assessment, total emissions need to include both operational emissions (Scope 1 and Scope 2) and embodied emissions (Scope 3). Operational emissions refer to direct emissions from sources controlled by the RI or indirect emissions from purchased electricity sources, calculated based on total measured energy consumption. Embodied emissions refer to indirect GHG emissions from raw material acquisition, production, and end-of-life (EoL) treatment [6]. They should be estimated or disclosed based on available supplier data, environmental product declarations, lifecycle databases, or standard freight emission factors. Embodied emissions should also include transportation where transport emissions are not already included in supplier-provided emission factors.

Calculation methodology: 1) Collect total operational energy consumption data per year (kWh). Multiply by regional or supplier-specific emission factors (kg CO₂-eq/kWh). The European Environment Agency reports that in 2021 each kWh of electricity in the EU emitted on average 0.226 kg CO₂-eq/kWh [13].

2) Collect data from embodied carbon: Gather information on a) all materials, components, and equipment contributing to embodied emissions, including raw material types and quantities (metals, plastics, batteries, cooling fluids, etc.), b) production energy and process emissions, and c) end-of-life treatment and associated energy use. Multiply data by appropriate embodied emission factors (kg CO₂-eq/unit).

3) Where transportation is not included in the embodied emission factors, calculate transport emissions using mass, distance, and mode-specific freight emission factors (kg CO₂-eq/tonne-km) [14], and add these to the embodied emissions.

GWP = Operational emissions + Embodied emissions

Where:

Operational emissions = $\sum(\text{Energy} \times \text{Emission factor})$

Embodied emissions = $\sum(\text{Quantity of material or component} \times \text{Embodied emission factor}) + \sum(\text{Transport activity} \times \text{Transport emission factor})$

5.2 Energy

Indicator: Total primary energy demand (MJ)

Metrics: Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) is a commonly used metric in Lifecycle Assessments to measure the total primary energy demand used directly and indirectly throughout the lifecycle of a product, system, or service. The CED usually takes into consideration the full lifecycle, including raw materials, manufacturing, transport, use, and end-of-life (EoL).

Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) is a widely used KPI for data centres to assess the energy efficiency of infrastructure by measuring the ratio of total data centre energy consumption to the energy used by IT equipment. A lower PUE value indicates higher energy efficiency.

While CED can be used for the purpose of cross-cutting information gathering across all the lifecycle phases, the PUE can be used to provide more context for the efficiency of the operational phase.

Calculation methodology:

$CED = \Sigma (\text{Operational energy in MJ}) + \Sigma (\text{embodied energy from production, maintenance, EoL})$

$PUE = \text{Total facility power} / \text{IT equipment power}$

5.3 Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE)

Indicators: Total WEEE (kg), % of WEEE recycled

Metrics: Mass of electronic hardware discarded at end-of-life (EoL). Proportion of WEEE that is recycled, reused, or recovered.

Calculation methodology: 1) Inventory of hardware replaced or decommissioned. 2) Apply average weights by device category (e.g., servers, switches, drives). 3) Track or estimate EoL treatment route: recycled, reused, discarded, etc. Use supplier or industry data when direct information is unavailable.

$WEEE (kg) = \Sigma (\text{mass of each discarded device (kg)} \times \text{Quantity discarded})$

$\% \text{ Recycled} = (\text{Recycled WEEE} / \text{Total WEEE}) \times 100$

5.4 Water

Indicators: Total Water Use (litres), Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE)

Metrics: Total volume of water consumed by the infrastructure. WUE indicates litres of water used per unit of IT equipment energy consumption.

Calculation methodology: 1) Sum direct water usage (i.e. in cooling systems). Include embedded water use from manufacturing where possible. 2) Divide by kWh of IT energy.

$WUE = \text{Litres of water used} / \text{kWh of IT energy}$

6 Environmental impact assessment methodology framework

6.1 Use of the GreenDIGIT self-assessment questionnaire

This section of the deliverable will outline the framework of the environmental impact assessment methodology. It provides instructions and context for the steps to identify and assess environmental impacts of RIs, identify actions to mitigate negative impact, prioritise actions, and monitor impact post-evaluation. The methodology consists of six steps (see figure 3), which need to be carried out in a consecutive order by an appointed RI Reviewer.

Figure 3: Complete methodology steps.

The GreenDIGIT environmental impact assessment methodology needs to be practically carried out using the GreenDIGIT self-assessment questionnaire (SAQ). The SAQ is reported on in detail in Deliverable **D8.1** [2]. The methodology provides a theoretical base for the assessment while the questionnaire offers a practical tool to implement the assessment. These two efforts have been developed in tandem to deliver a joint service for RIs to help assess their overall environmental footprint ex ante and set in place an action plan to monitor and report on progress ex post. Figure 4 provides an overview of the relationship and structure of the self-assessment questionnaire and the impact assessment methodology.

The self-assessment questionnaire covers several areas of sustainability that are pertinent for assessing an RIs' overall impacts, including:

- Energy Efficiency and Decarbonisation
- Environmental Monitoring and Impact
- Pollution, Waste, and Circularity
- Water and Ecosystems
- Lifecycle integration
- Governance and Compliance
- Stakeholder Engagement and Awareness

Each area is divided into a set of questions that address different phases of the RI lifecycle with some listed as cross-cutting, meaning that the question addresses several or all lifecycle phases. The lifecycle assessment phases are defined according to phases from the ESFRI lifecycle approach, as defined for

the ESFRI Roadmap (see figure 1). As explained in section 4.3 ‘RI lifecycle and system boundaries’ of this deliverable and outlined in figure 2, the methodology can be used to assess the overall lifecycle. Although several questions in the self-assessment questionnaire are focused on operation phase activities as the direct RI impact, others require the RI to also assess relevant activities along earlier or later lifecycle phases or to consider the cross-cutting nature of activities from cradle to grave.

In accordance with the outlined methodology requirements (see section 4.2), the methodology assesses comparable dimensions and categories that represent a large part of the total environmental impact. Therefore, the self-assessment questionnaire can be used as a filter to scope questions that directly assess the four impact categories (climate change, energy, waste, water). Other questions listed with a ‘non-environmental’ tag, including governance and stakeholder engagement, are also required to form a complete overview of the RI’s environmental actions, including the role of external providers and stakeholders in the indirect impacts of the RI activities.

The following sub-sections will explain each step in detail.

Figure 4: Merging of Environmental Impact Assessment Methodology and Self-assessment Questionnaire.

6.2 Step 1: Identification of scope and target capability levels

WHAT? The **first step** of the methodology consists of identifying the scope and target capability levels for the assessment. In the self-assessment questionnaire, the RI Reviewer must filter the scope

individually for each topic. It is recommended that the RI Reviewer begins with all processes and results that are relevant unless they have guidance in setting and appropriating the scope and fitting goals.

HOW? First, the RI Reviewer needs to select desired topic areas for the scope. See table 6. Then, for each topic in scope, the RI Reviewer needs to select a target capability level, which they desire to reach as an outcome after the assessment. The RI Reviewer should take into consideration which level they can practically strive towards in context to their own maturity and resources. The target capability levels range from Level 1 Ad-hoc / Initial, to Level 2 Developing / Partial, and finally Level 3 Established / Assured. See table 7.

Table 6: Identification of scope and impacts in self-assessment questionnaire.

Scope and Goals	In Scope?	Target Capability level?
Governance and Compliance		
G1: Alignment with relevant EU regulations (CSRD, ESRS, EED, ESPR, WEEE, LCA, ISO14040, ISO14044)	No	Select...
G2: Existence of a formal environmental sustainability strategy	No	Select...
G3: Defined roles and responsibilities for sustainability	No	Select...
G4: Inclusion of sustainability in internal policies or quality systems	No	Select...
G5: Inclusion of sustainability in procurement or supplier management	No	Select...
Stakeholder Engagement and Awareness		
S1: Sustainability awareness/training for staff	No	Select...
S2: Involvement of stakeholders in environmental planning	No	Select...
S3: Transparent communication of environmental performance	No	Select...
Energy Efficiency and Decarbonisation		
E1: Adoption of renewable energy sources	Yes	Select...
E2: AI-driven workload or energy optimisation	Yes	Select...
E3: Waste heat recovery or reuse strategies	Yes	Select...
E4: Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) tracking and optimisation	Yes	Select...
E5: Carbon Use Effectiveness (CUE) tracking and reduction	Yes	Select...
E6: Flexible energy usage or smart grid responsiveness	Yes	Select...
Environmental Monitoring and Impact		
M1: Measurement of environmental KPIs (GHG, energy, water, waste)	Yes	Select...
M2: Use of environmental metrics in planning and reporting	Yes	Select...
M3: Lifecycle-based environmental impact assessment (based on LCA methodology)	Yes	Select...
M4: Use of WUE (Water Usage Effectiveness) or similar water metrics	Yes	Select...
M5: Implementation of monitoring tools/platforms	Yes	Select...
Pollution, Waste, and Circularity		
P1: Reduction of operational waste (incl. e-waste)	Yes	Select...
P2: End-of-life management for equipment	Yes	Select...
P3: Circular IT practices (reuse, remanufacturing, modularity)	Yes	Select...
P4: Pollution control (air, water, soil)	Yes	Select...
P5: Use of low-impact or non-toxic materials	Yes	Select...
Water and Ecosystems		
W1: Water usage monitoring and reduction strategies	Yes	Select...
W2: Impact on local ecosystems or biodiversity	Yes	Select...
W3: Rainwater harvesting, reuse, or runoff management	Yes	Select...
W4: Water-based cooling systems and water efficiency strategies	Yes	Select...
Lifecycle Integration		
L1: Sustainability embedded in the design phase	Yes	Select...
L2: Consideration of sustainability during implementation	Yes	Select...
L3: Operational sustainability practices	Yes	Select...
L4: Decommissioning/termination phase planning	Yes	Select...

Table 7: Capability levels.

Capability level	Description
Level 1: Ad-hoc / Initial	Awareness is minimal and practices are largely unstructured.

Level 2: Developing / Partial	Some measures exist, but they are inconsistent or not formalised.
Level 3: Established / Assured	The RI is confident that the topic is systematically addressed with well-defined practices.

6.3 Step 2: Assessment of impacts and current capability levels

WHAT? The **second step** of the methodology consists of forming an assessment of impacts and current capability levels of each topic area selected for the scope. In order to complete the environmental impact assessment, the RI Reviewer must answer all self-assessment questions across the topic areas selected for the assessment scope.

HOW? In the beginning of the assessment, the RI Reviewer should form an **inventory of the RI components** to be used for gathering data for the impact categories (see section 4.4), which can be used to record the evidence and rationale for score in the self-assessment questionnaire. The inventory of RI components should then be used as a baseline for the RI Reviewer to systematically gather data across the RI components to answer the self-assessment questionnaire questions. Where information may be unavailable or not yet in operation, an estimate of expected usage should be used.

For each topic and question in scope, the RI Reviewer must **select a self-assessment score of 1 to 3** to determine their current capability level. Each capability level is contextualised to the question at hand to help the RI Reviewer correctly assess their level. See example of the capability level distribution for renewable energy consumption from table 8.

Table 8: Example of self-assessment scoring during step 2.

Question	Lifecycle Phase	Environmental Dimension	Associated Metric	Reference (Standard/Policy)	Impact Magnitude	Impact Likelihood	Improvement Priority	Capability Level	Descriptions
What proportion of the RI's energy consumption is sourced from renewable energy, and how is this verified?	Operation	Energy	% of energy from renewable sources	ISO 50001, ESRS E1, EU Renewable Energy Directive	High	High	High	1	The RI does not use or track renewable energy usage.
					Medium	Medium	Medium	2	Some energy comes from renewable sources, but tracking is limited or informal.
					Low	Low	Low	3	A high proportion of energy is sourced from renewables, verified through formal documentation or contracts.

The chosen self-assessment score from 1 to 3 is complemented by a corresponding improvement priority to determine how crucial it is for the RI to set up improvement actions to improve their sustainability practices, categorised by a scale of low-medium-high. Step 4 will delve into the measurement methodology of the priority level determination.

6.4 Step 3: Identification of actions

WHAT? The **third step** of the methodology offers an overview of recommended actions for the RI to undertake as a response to the assessment from step 2. For each question answered in step 2, the self-assessment questionnaire provides a corresponding action item specified for the identified level. This way, the RI can gather a repertoire of actions that are personalised to their current capability level.

HOW? After the RI Reviewer has determined their self-assessment score based on their capability level, the questionnaire will automatically match it to a corresponding recommended action item. A recommended action is provided for each question in the self-assessment questionnaire to help the RI reach a higher capability level or to maintain a sufficient level of sustainability if the highest level has

already been reached. See table 9 as an example of recommended action items for a question about renewable energy consumption.

Table 9: Example of identification of actions during step 3.

Capability Level	Descriptions	Recommended Action
1	The RI does not use or track renewable energy usage.	Assess the current energy mix and identify opportunities to procure or transition to renewable energy sources. Start collecting data and documentation to verify sources (e.g. supplier declarations, energy certificates).
2	Some energy comes from renewable sources, but tracking is limited or informal.	Increase the share of renewable energy through updated contracts or on-site generation. Implement processes for regular verification and reporting (e.g. through Guarantees of Origin, utility audits).
3	A high proportion of energy is sourced from renewables, verified through formal documentation or contracts.	No action needed. Continue monitoring and ensure transparency in reporting renewable energy sourcing and verification.

6.5 Step 4: Determination of priority levels

WHAT? It is important to differentiate and prioritise the most relevant impacts and actions to define the action plan and to allocate resources in an impactful manner. To achieve this, the **fourth step** of the methodology consists of a determination of priority levels to underscore the relative urgency of improving a capability level (improvement priority) and to identify the most important actions to undertake (implementation priority).

The level of priority is classified on a scale of low-medium-high and is determined based upon the following assessment parameters:

1. **Level of impact magnitude and likelihood to determine the improvement priority of identified impacts.** This step gives context to the self-assessment scores during step 2 by determining how significant the impact magnitudes are. The magnitude scale measures the scale of the impact, whereas likelihood measures the scale of impact probability. Based on these parameters, the level of improvement priority can be determined.
2. **Level of the improvement priority and effort required to determine the implementation priority of recommended actions.** This step takes the result of the previous improvement priority and assesses it against the amount of effort required to implement the corresponding recommended action. Based on these parameters, the level of implementation priority can be determined. This step provides insights into the action plan (step 5 of the methodology) by helping RIs identify the actions that provide low-hanging fruits to implement with maximum impact and minimal effort.

Figure 5: Improvement and implementation priority assessment parameters.

See below tables 10, 11, and 12 for an overview of the low-medium-high scale definitions for assessing the three parameters: magnitude, likelihood, and effort required.

Table 10: Assessment scale levels for ‘magnitude’ parameter.

Scale	Magnitude of impacts
High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extensive duration of negative impacts (10+ years) • Evident spill-over to external stakeholders • Significant harm potential
Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderate duration of negative impacts (3-10 years) • Threat of spill-over to external stakeholders • Moderate harm potential
Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brief to no duration of negative impacts • Threat restricted to internal stakeholders • Little to no harm

Table 11: Assessment scale levels for ‘likelihood’ parameter.

Scale	Likelihood
High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Imminent and probable impact.
Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Noteworthy but not overly imminent impact.
Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unlikely or low probability impact.

Table 12: Assessment scale levels for ‘effort required’ parameter.

Scale	Effort required
High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involves a significant level of resources, effort, or investment. • Potential efforts and investment may outweigh associated benefits.
Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires a moderate level of resources, effort, or investment. • Potential benefits are balanced with effort and investment.
Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demands minimal resources, effort, or investment. • Potential benefits outweigh effort and investment.

HOW? To easily categorise the priority levels, the methodology provides two matrixes (see tables 13 and 14) to serve as keys for determining the respective priority levels of improvement and implementation.

Table 13: Matrix for improvement priority level determination.

		Likelihood		
		High	Medium	Low
Magnitude	High	high	high	medium
	Medium	high	medium	low
	Low	medium	low	low

Table 14: Matrix for implementation priority level determination.

		Effort Required		
		High	Medium	Low
Improvement priority	High	planned	urgent	immediate
	Medium	low	planned	urgent
	Low	no action needed	low	planned

The improvement priorities will be automatically calculated in the self-assessment questionnaire based on the self-assessment score, which the RI Reviewer selects during step 2. The capability level is matched by a pre-determined level of magnitude and likelihood, which form the improvement priority for each question in scope for the self-assessment questionnaire. The level of magnitude and likelihood have been matched to fit each capability level, taking into consideration each topic’s overall magnitude in the context of environmental sustainability.

Once the improvement priorities have been selected for each question in the self-assessment questionnaire, the RI Reviewer must assess the level of effort required for each corresponding action item by selecting the estimated level (based on the definitions in table 12). The implementation priority will then be automatically calculated in the self-assessment questionnaire using the logic from table 14. This will provide the RI with a detailed list of prioritised action items to help them formalise the action plan and to allocate resources in an impactful manner. The priorities are categorised according to the matrix into: 1) No action needed, 2) Low, 3) Planned, 4) Urgent, 5) Immediate. See table 15 for the definition of each implementation priority level.

Table 15: Results of the implementation priority.

Implementation priority level	Meaning
Immediate	Top priority, quick win or urgent fix – act now.
Urgent	Needs addressing soon – schedule in near term.
Planned	Include in standard planning – not urgent but necessary.
Low	Can be postponed or handled when convenient.
No action needed	Either already sufficient or not impactful enough.

6.6 Step 5: Formalising the action plan

WHAT? Once the recommended actions have been identified based on the self-assessment score and the prioritisation of actions has been determined, the methodology recommends the RI to formalise a full action plan with internal agreements within the RI management.

HOW? To complete the action plan, a leader and a deadline should be defined for each identified action that is prioritised as **‘planned’**, **‘high’** or **‘immediate’**. Any relevant remarks should also be noted for internal planning. Table 16 demonstrates an example table for formalising the action plan, which can also be used for monitoring purposes by the RI Reviewer.

Table 16: Example table for monitoring Action Plan.

Implementation Priority	Leader	Deadline	Status	Remarks
Urgent	Leader 1	01.01.2026	Recommended actions to be started in 2 months.	No remarks.
Planned	Leader 1	31.08.2026	Recommended actions to be started in 2026.	No remarks.
Immediate	Leader 1	31.10.2025	Recommended actions starting.	No remarks.
Urgent	Leader 2	01.01.2026	Recommended actions to be started in 2 months.	No remarks.
Planned	Leader 2	31.08.2026	Recommended actions to be started in 2026.	No remarks.
No Action Needed	N/A	N/A	N/A	No remarks.
Immediate	Leader 3	31.10.2025	Recommended actions starting.	No remarks.
Urgent	Leader 3	01.01.2026	Recommended Actions to be started in 2 months.	No remarks.
Urgent	Leader 3	01.01.2026	Recommended actions to be started in 2 months.	No remarks.
Planned	Leader 3	31.08.2026	Recommended actions to be started in 2026.	No remarks.

6.7 Step 6: Monitoring and reporting

WHAT? In the final **step six** of the methodology, the appointed RI Reviewer should monitor the implementation of the action plan.

HOW? The appointed RI Reviewer should update and review the analysis whenever the RI undergoes any substantial change that may impact the action plan. They should keep the ‘Status’ column of table 16 up to date on a regular basis. We invite the Reviewer to provide a report at the end of the set deadline or on an annual basis to record the actions achieved by the RI.

7 Use case application and validation

This section presents the application and validation of the GreenDIGIT Environmental Impact Assessment Methodology through four use cases involving the project’s participating Research Infrastructures (RIs): **EBRAINS**, **EGI**, **SoBigData**, and **SLICES** – four major distributed Digital Research Infrastructures at different lifecycle stages. See figure 6 for an overview of the RIs’ current stages.

Following the development and integration of the self-assessment questionnaire with the methodology, initial internal testing was conducted, after which the assessment was opened for broader testing in real-world operational RI environments. Each RI applied the methodology within its own infrastructure to verify its relevance, usability, and accuracy under actual operational conditions where available. The results of these assessments are presented in the following sub-sections through summary tables, which include self-assessment scores, recommended actions, and their categorisation in terms of improvement priority, effort required, and implementation priority.

This validation phase contributes to achieving Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 6, confirming that the methodology functions as a system prototype verified in operational settings, and supports RIs in prioritising concrete measures to reduce their environmental impact.

Figure 6: Participating RIs’ lifecycle stages.

7.1 RI 1 Use case – EBRAINS

Table 17: EBRAINS RI use case overview.

Question	Self-assessment score (1-2-3)	Recommended Action	Improvement Priority	Effort Required	Implementation Priority
Governance and Compliance					
To what extent is the RI aligned with relevant EU environmental regulations such as CSRD, ESRS, EED, ESPR, WEEE, LCA, ISO14040, ISO14044?	1 - EBRAINS RI provides access to high-performance computing resources, as well as neuromorphic computing systems, via its members. Our infrastructure providers offer their services to the RI as in-kind contributions, and we have some evidence of their adherence to the EU regulations.	Conduct a regulatory gap analysis to identify which EU environmental regulations apply and where the RI is currently non-compliant. Engage legal or compliance expertise to support interpretation if needed.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Has the RI conducted a review or gap analysis to identify which regulations apply and how they are addressed?	1 - EBRAINS RI provides access to high-performance computing resources, as well as neuromorphic computing systems, via its members. Our infrastructure providers offer their services to the RI as in-kind contributions, and we have some evidence of their adherence to the EU regulations.	Initiate a structured regulatory review to identify applicable EU regulations (e.g. CSRD, ESRS, EED, ESPR, WEEE). Engage relevant internal or external expertise and document initial findings.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Is there a documented environmental sustainability strategy in place, endorsed by leadership and periodically updated?	1 - At this point in time, EBRAINS RI has informal environmental sustainability strategy. This will need to be synchronised with the hardware infrastructure providers.	Draft a documented environmental sustainability strategy that outlines goals, scope, and key priorities. Secure leadership engagement to initiate endorsement.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority

Are roles and responsibilities for environmental sustainability clearly assigned across relevant functions within the RI?	2 - EBRAINS AISBL/RI is right now in transformation mode to EDIC. And as research infrastructure is evolving, so are the roles and responsibilities of employees.	Document the assigned responsibilities formally (e.g. in organisational charts, role descriptions, quality systems) and ensure they are communicated internally.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
To what extent is environmental sustainability integrated into the RI's internal policies, management systems, or quality frameworks?	2 - Some RI policies make reference to sustainability, but integration is limited.	Expand integration of sustainability elements across internal systems. Ensure alignment with recognised frameworks such as ISO 14001 or ISO 9001 (with sustainability add-ons), and involve relevant departments in updates.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Does the RI include environmental sustainability criteria in procurement processes and supplier evaluations?	2 - In EBRAINS RI environmental criteria are used during the procurement for some products, however not across all procurement strategies.	Expand and formalise sustainability criteria in procurement documents and supplier contracts. Ensure criteria are measurable and consistently applied across purchases.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Stakeholder Engagement and Awareness					
To what extent does the RI provide staff training or awareness programmes on environmental sustainability topics relevant to their roles?	2 - Some trainings are planning to happen in the future, but they will not be systematic.	Establish structured training programmes with role-specific content. Include periodic refreshers and track staff participation and feedback.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Are relevant stakeholders (e.g. users, suppliers, partners) engaged in environmental planning or sustainability goal-setting processes?	2 - During the regular meetings with our partners within RI, stakeholder input is usually welcome; however, not consistently applied.	Develop a structured stakeholder engagement plan that includes regular input into sustainability planning or goal-setting processes. Document outcomes and integrate feedback.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Does the RI regularly communicate its environmental performance, actions, or goals to internal and external stakeholders?	1 - EBRAINS RI doesn't communicate environmental performance externally or internally. However, we have added a sustainability report from one of our hardware infrastructure	Identify key performance metrics and develop internal channels for sharing environmental information (e.g. newsletters, intranet updates).	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority

	partners (they offer an in-kind contribution and allow the RI services to run on their hardware infrastructure).				
Energy Efficiency and Decarbonisation					
What proportion of the RI's energy consumption is sourced from renewable energy, and how is this verified?	1 - EBRAINS RI is using hardware from our partners, and they are tracking energy usage for the whole operational stage, so that it will be difficult to track energy usage only for EBRAINS RI. Some of our members' energy consumption is sourced entirely from certified green sources.	Assess the current energy mix and identify opportunities to procure or transition to renewable energy sources. Start collecting data and documentation to verify sources (e.g. supplier declarations, energy certificates).	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Are AI or automation systems used to optimise energy consumption across compute, cooling, or other infrastructure components?	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not In Scope	Not In Scope	Not in Scope
Does the RI implement strategies to recover or reuse waste heat generated by infrastructure?	2 - EBRAINS RI is using hardware from our partners, and one of our partners implemented strategies to recover/reuse waste heat generated by infrastructure	Implement basic heat recovery systems where feasible. Monitor effectiveness and explore opportunities to expand reuse or integrate with external systems.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Is the RI's PUE monitored regularly, and are efforts in place to optimise it over time?	1 - EBRAINS RI is using the hardware from our partners, they track PUE and one of our partners achieved certification under the ISO 50001:2018.	Begin monitoring Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) at a basic level. Install or configure metering infrastructure to enable regular data collection.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Is CUE calculated and used as a metric for assessing carbon performance of the RI's operations?	2 - EBRAINS RI is using the hardware and cloud resources from our partners, they are actively tracking CUE, but it is not	Implement regular CUE calculations and use the results to identify inefficiencies or opportunities for emissions reduction.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority

	actively used in RI's decision-making.	Integrate CUE into internal sustainability reporting.			
Does the RI participate in energy flexibility initiatives, such as demand response or smart grid integration?	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not In Scope	Not In Scope	Not in Scope
Environmental Monitoring and Impact					
Which environmental KPIs (e.g. GHG emissions, energy, water, waste) are currently measured and how frequently are they reported?	1 - At this moment, EBRAINS RI is not measuring /reporting environmental KPIs directly. Each member that is making their hardware infrastructure available to the RI, is monitoring and reporting their KPI independently and according to the rules and regulations in their respective country.	Identify key environmental KPIs relevant to RI operations. Begin collecting basic data on at least one dimension (e.g. energy use or waste generation) and define a reporting cadence.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
To what extent are environmental metrics integrated into the RI's strategic planning or operational decision-making?	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not In Scope	Not In Scope	Not in Scope
Has the RI conducted or applied lifecycle assessments (LCA) to evaluate its environmental impact across different phases, including monitoring of Global Warming Potential (GWP) and Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)?	1	Build internal awareness of LCA methods and identify opportunities to apply LCA to RI infrastructure or service components. Consider piloting an LCA for a specific lifecycle phase or asset.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Is WUE or any comparable metric tracked and used to	1 - EBRAINS RI is using the hardware from our partners and they track WUE , but for RI is	Review current water usage practices and assess the feasibility of applying Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE) or a	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority

assess the RI's water efficiency performance?	not used in performance management.	comparable metric. Begin collecting relevant data where possible.			
Are dedicated tools or platforms in place for tracking, visualising, or reporting environmental performance?	1 - EBRAINS RI does not have dedicated environmental monitoring tools or platforms.	Identify suitable tools or platforms for environmental data tracking and reporting. Evaluate whether existing systems (e.g. monitoring software, spreadsheets) meet reporting needs.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Pollution, Waste, and Circularity					
Are practices in place to reduce operational waste generation, including e-waste from IT systems and equipment?	1 - EBRAINS RI is using hardware from our partners, and they have partial practices for waste minimisation.	Identify main sources of operational and e-waste. Begin implementing basic waste reduction measures (e.g. paperless processes, proper e-waste disposal procedures).	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Does the RI apply defined procedures for the reuse, recycling, or proper disposal of decommissioned equipment?	2 - In EBRAINS RI, some practices exist, for equipment that we have. As an example: we have informal policy for decommissioning laptops, printers, cartridges, servers.	Implement procedures and ensure responsible parties follow them consistently. Track decommissioned assets and apply certified disposal or reuse practices.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Are circular IT principles such as reuse, modularity, or refurbishment applied in procurement or infrastructure management?	1 - Our partners consider IT principles (reuse, refurbishment) in their operation and apply them in the infrastructure management.	Review procurement and infrastructure policies to identify opportunities to apply circular IT principles (e.g. reuse, modular design, refurbishment). Begin piloting circular approaches in select areas.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Are measures in place to monitor and manage pollution risks related to air, water, or soil emissions from RI operations?	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not In Scope	Not In Scope	Not in Scope
Are environmental criteria applied when selecting materials or products, with preference for low-impact or non-toxic options?	2 - EBRAINS RI apply inconsistently some environmental criteria (like: European energy label while selecting the products).	Formalise and apply environmental criteria across material/product procurement. Refer to ecolabels or standards (e.g. EU Ecolabel, ISO 14024) where applicable.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority

Water and Ecosystems					
To what extent does the RI monitor its water consumption and implement strategies to reduce it?	1 - EBRAINS RI is using hardware and cloud resources from our partners, and they track water and have reduction measures in their organisation.	Begin monitoring water usage across relevant operations. Identify key consumption points and explore opportunities for reduction (e.g. fixture upgrades, behavioural campaigns).	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Does the RI assess and manage its potential impacts on local ecosystems or biodiversity, particularly for physical infrastructure?	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not In Scope	Not In Scope	Not in Scope
Are there systems or practices in place for rainwater harvesting, water reuse, or managing stormwater runoff?	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not In Scope	Not In Scope	Not in Scope
Does the RI use water-based cooling systems, and are measures in place to optimise their water efficiency and minimise environmental impact?	1 - EBRAINS RI is using the hardware and cloud resources from our partners, and they track water consumption for cooling. Environmental considerations are acknowledged by EBRAINS RI, however not systematically applied.	Begin tracking water usage related to cooling systems. Identify inefficiencies and research available technologies for reducing consumption or shifting to closed-loop or hybrid systems.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Lifecycle Integration					
To what extent are sustainability considerations integrated into the design and planning of new infrastructure or services?	2 - As the EBRAINS RI structure is evolving, the sustainability aspects are more present. We are developing the lifecycle for our services, with different levels. With this evolution, we will also see the integration with hardware infrastructure lifecycles.	Embed defined sustainability criteria into design frameworks, including materials selection, energy efficiency, and end-of-life considerations. Document decisions and outcomes.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority

<p>Are sustainability criteria applied during the implementation or deployment of infrastructure components and systems?</p>	<p>2 - As the EBRAINS RI structure is evolving, the sustainability aspects are more present. We are developing the lifecycle for our services, with different levels. With this evolution, we will also see the integration with hardware infrastructure lifecycles.</p>	<p>No action needed. Maintain and review implementation practices to ensure continued alignment with sustainability standards and operational objectives.</p>	<p>Medium improvement priority</p>	<p>Medium effort required</p>	<p>Planned implementation priority</p>
<p>What sustainability practices are in place for the operation and maintenance of the RI's infrastructure and services?</p>	<p>1 - Within EBRAINS RI, the partners have implemented some sustainability practices that are in place, and they are monitoring energy consumption, for example. However, these metrics are not monitored at RI level.</p>	<p>Identify operational areas where sustainability practices can be introduced (e.g. energy management, resource efficiency, preventive maintenance). Begin applying basic principles.</p>	<p>High improvement priority</p>	<p>Medium effort required</p>	<p>Urgent implementation priority</p>
<p>Does the RI include environmental considerations in its decommissioning or termination plans for infrastructure or services?</p>	<p>1 - EBRAINS RI has end-of-life measures for software and data storage, and hardware; however, not all of them are formally applied. EBRAINS RI does not control the end-of-life policies that are in place at each hardware infrastructure site, as this is an in-kind contribution to the RI.</p>	<p>Review existing decommissioning or termination procedures and identify gaps related to environmental impact (e.g. equipment disposal, site remediation). Draft basic guidelines for responsible end-of-life practices.</p>	<p>High improvement priority</p>	<p>Medium effort required</p>	<p>Urgent implementation priority</p>

Comment from EBRAINS RI after completing the questionnaire:

After completing the self-assessment questionnaire, we identified key actions that need to be addressed moving forward.

EBRAINS RI relies on the hardware infrastructure provided by our partners, and we trust that they are committed to using renewable energy sources and implementing sustainable practices across their operations. However, it is not currently possible to isolate RI's specific energy consumption, as the hardware is shared with other organisations. This limitation also applies to other environmental KPIs, such as water consumption and waste management. We are able to share supporting information—such as articles and sustainability reports—when they are made publicly available by our partners.

EBRAINS RI has some environmental policies in place, though many are informal or tailored to specific products. For example, the procurement team informally considers environmental factors when sourcing certain hardware, but there is no formalised policy governing this process.

7.2 RI 2 Use case – SoBigData

Table 18: SoBigData RI use case overview.

Question	Self-assessment score (1-2-3)	Recommended Action	Improvement Priority	Effort Required	Implementation Priority
Governance and Compliance					
To what extent is the RI aligned with relevant EU environmental regulations such as CSRD, ESRS, EED, ESPR, WEEE, LCA, ISO14040, ISO14044?	2	Update internal documentation and procedures to close identified regulatory gaps. Begin implementing key compliance actions with clear timelines and responsibilities.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Has the RI conducted a review or gap analysis to identify which regulations apply and how they are addressed?	2	Expand and update the regulatory gap analysis. Clarify which obligations are partially addressed, and prepare an action plan to resolve any gaps identified.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Is there a documented environmental sustainability strategy in place, endorsed by leadership and periodically updated?	1	Draft a documented environmental sustainability strategy that outlines goals, scope, and key priorities. Secure leadership engagement to initiate endorsement.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Are roles and responsibilities for environmental sustainability clearly	1	Identify key functions and assign clear responsibilities for environmental sustainability. Ensure responsibility is not	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority

assigned across relevant functions within the RI?		siload but shared across operational and strategic roles.			
To what extent is environmental sustainability integrated into the RI's internal policies, management systems, or quality frameworks?	2	Expand integration of sustainability elements across internal systems. Ensure alignment with recognised frameworks such as ISO 14001 or ISO 9001 (with sustainability add-ons), and involve relevant departments in updates.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Does the RI include environmental sustainability criteria in procurement processes and supplier evaluations?	2	Expand and formalise sustainability criteria in procurement documents and supplier contracts. Ensure criteria are measurable and consistently applied across purchases.	Medium improvement priority	High effort required	Low implementation priority
Stakeholder Engagement and Awareness					
To what extent does the RI provide staff training or awareness programmes on environmental sustainability topics relevant to their roles?	1	Develop and deliver basic sustainability awareness sessions for staff. Tailor content to general operational relevance and RI objectives.	High improvement priority	Low effort required	Immediate implementation priority
Are relevant stakeholders (e.g. users, suppliers, partners) engaged in environmental planning or sustainability goal-setting processes?	2	Develop a structured stakeholder engagement plan that includes regular input into sustainability planning or goal-setting processes. Document outcomes and integrate feedback.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Does the RI regularly communicate its environmental performance, actions, or goals to internal and external stakeholders?	2	Identify key performance metrics and develop internal channels for sharing environmental information (e.g. newsletters, intranet updates).	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Energy Efficiency and Decarbonisation					

What proportion of the RI's energy consumption is sourced from renewable energy, and how is this verified?	2	Increase the share of renewable energy through updated contracts or on-site generation. Implement processes for regular verification and reporting (e.g. through Guarantees of Origin, utility audits).	Medium improvement priority	High effort required	Low implementation priority
Are AI or automation systems used to optimise energy consumption across compute, cooling, or other infrastructure components?	1	Identify infrastructure areas with high energy use and evaluate the potential of AI or automation tools for energy optimisation. Initiate pilot projects or feasibility assessments.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Does the RI implement strategies to recover or reuse waste heat generated by infrastructure?	1	Assess the feasibility of heat recovery based on infrastructure type and thermal load. Identify potential use cases (e.g. heating buildings, district heating, internal reuse).	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Is the RI's PUE monitored regularly, and are efforts in place to optimise it over time?	1	Begin monitoring Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) at a basic level. Install or configure metering infrastructure to enable regular data collection.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Is CUE calculated and used as a metric for assessing carbon performance of the RI's operations?	1	Familiarise the team with Carbon Usage Effectiveness (CUE) and assess whether sufficient data exists to begin basic calculations. Identify carbon-intensive operational areas.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Does the RI participate in energy flexibility initiatives, such as demand response or smart grid integration?	2	Participate in one or more energy flexibility initiatives. Establish internal protocols for responding to external grid signals or adjusting loads dynamically.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Environmental Monitoring and Impact					
Which environmental KPIs (e.g. GHG emissions, energy, water, waste) are currently measured and	1	Identify key environmental KPIs relevant to RI operations. Begin collecting basic data on at least one dimension (e.g.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority

how frequently are they reported?		energy use or waste generation) and define a reporting cadence.			
To what extent are environmental metrics integrated into the RI's strategic planning or operational decision-making?	1	Identify opportunities to integrate basic environmental metrics (e.g. energy use, GHG emissions) into routine planning or procurement decisions. Raise awareness among decision-makers.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Has the RI conducted or applied lifecycle assessments (LCA) to evaluate its environmental impact across different phases, including monitoring of Global Warming Potential (GWP) and Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)?	1	Build internal awareness of LCA methods and identify opportunities to apply LCA to RI infrastructure or service components. Consider piloting an LCA for a specific lifecycle phase or asset.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Is WUE or any comparable metric tracked and used to assess the RI's water efficiency performance?	1	Review current water usage practices and assess the feasibility of applying Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE) or a comparable metric. Begin collecting relevant data where possible.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Are dedicated tools or platforms in place for tracking, visualising, or reporting environmental performance?	1	Identify suitable tools or platforms for environmental data tracking and reporting. Evaluate whether existing systems (e.g. monitoring software, spreadsheets) meet reporting needs.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Pollution, Waste, and Circularity					
Are practices in place to reduce operational waste generation, including e-waste from IT systems and equipment?	3	No action needed. Maintain active reduction strategies and consider partnerships for certified e-waste recycling or donation schemes.	Low improvement priority	Medium effort required	Low implementation priority
Does the RI apply defined procedures for the reuse, recycling, or proper	3	No action needed. Maintain procedures and consider auditing or reporting	Low improvement priority	Medium effort required	Low implementation priority

disposal of decommissioned equipment?		results to enhance transparency and continuous improvement.			
Are circular IT principles such as reuse, modularity, or refurbishment applied in procurement or infrastructure management?	2	Integrate circular IT requirements into procurement specifications and asset management practices. Collaborate with suppliers to support reuse or refurbishment options.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Are measures in place to monitor and manage pollution risks related to air, water, or soil emissions from RI operations?	1	Identify potential pollution risks across RI operations (air, water, soil). Begin planning basic monitoring or mitigation actions in line with legal and environmental standards.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Are environmental criteria applied when selecting materials or products, with preference for low-impact or non-toxic options?	3	No action needed. Maintain current procurement criteria and periodically review for alignment with updated sustainability requirements.	Low improvement priority	Low effort required	Planned implementation priority
Water and Ecosystems					
To what extent does the RI monitor its water consumption and implement strategies to reduce it?	1	Begin monitoring water usage across relevant operations. Identify key consumption points and explore opportunities for reduction (e.g. fixture upgrades, behavioural campaigns).	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Does the RI assess and manage its potential impacts on local ecosystems or biodiversity, particularly for physical infrastructure?	1	Conduct an initial review of how RI activities or infrastructure may affect local ecosystems or biodiversity. Identify areas of sensitivity and potential impact.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Are there systems or practices in place for rainwater harvesting, water	1	Assess site infrastructure to identify opportunities for rainwater harvesting or stormwater management. Begin	High improvement priority	Low effort required	Immediate implementation priority

reuse, or managing stormwater runoff?		feasibility studies or pilot planning for basic systems.			
Does the RI use water-based cooling systems, and are measures in place to optimise their water efficiency and minimise environmental impact?	1	Begin tracking water usage related to cooling systems. Identify inefficiencies and research available technologies for reducing consumption or shifting to closed-loop or hybrid systems.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Lifecycle Integration					
To what extent are sustainability considerations integrated into the design and planning of new infrastructure or services?	2	Embed defined sustainability criteria into design frameworks, including materials selection, energy efficiency, and end-of-life considerations. Document decisions and outcomes.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Are sustainability criteria applied during the implementation or deployment of infrastructure components and systems?	3	No action needed. Maintain and review implementation practices to ensure continued alignment with sustainability standards and operational objectives.	Low improvement priority	Low effort required	Planned implementation priority
What sustainability practices are in place for the operation and maintenance of the RI's infrastructure and services?	1	Identify operational areas where sustainability practices can be introduced (e.g. energy management, resource efficiency, preventive maintenance). Begin applying basic principles.	High improvement priority	Low effort required	Immediate implementation priority
Does the RI include environmental considerations in its decommissioning or termination plans for infrastructure or services?	2	Integrate formal environmental considerations into decommissioning plans, including reuse, recycling, and waste minimisation. Assign responsibilities and track execution.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority

Comment from SoBigData RI after completing the questionnaire:

After completing the self-assessment questionnaire, SoBigData RI has identified key areas that require further development to improve its environmental sustainability practices.

The RI relies on its own distributed infrastructure, composed of a central hub node located in Pisa and other nodes spread across mostly Italy. While this guarantees independence and flexibility, it also makes it challenging to measure and report environmental indicators (e.g. energy consumption, water usage, waste management) in a harmonised way across all nodes. At present, such data is not systematically monitored at RI level, limiting the ability to track and benchmark sustainability performance.

Some environmental practices already exist but are informal and heterogeneous across nodes. For example, sustainability considerations are occasionally taken into account in procurement and governance processes, but no formal RI-wide strategy or policy is currently in place. Roles and responsibilities for sustainability are also not clearly defined.

Moving forward, SoBigData RI will prioritise the definition of a formal sustainability policy, the assignment of clear responsibilities, and the development of coordinated monitoring practices across its nodes. These actions will strengthen compliance with EU frameworks and foster a more systematic culture of sustainability within the distributed infrastructure.

7.3 RI 3 Use case – EGI

Table 19: EGI RI use case overview.

Question	Self-assessment score (1-2-3)	Recommended Action	Improvement Priority	Effort Required	Implementation Priority
Governance and Compliance					
To what extent is the RI aligned with relevant EU environmental regulations such as CSRD, ESRS, EED, ESPR, WEEE, LCA, ISO14040, ISO14044?	1 - Majority of our institutes did not provide any evidence considering the given standards and regulations.	Conduct a regulatory gap analysis to identify which EU environmental regulations apply and where the RI is currently non-compliant. Engage legal or compliance expertise to support interpretation if needed.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Has the RI conducted a review or gap analysis to identify which regulations apply and how they are addressed?	1 - No gap analysis is performed so far in majority of our institutes.	Initiate a structured regulatory review to identify applicable EU regulations (e.g. CSRD, ESRS, EED, ESPR, WEEE). Engage relevant internal or external expertise and document initial findings.	High improvement priority	High effort required	Planned implementation priority

Is there a documented environmental sustainability strategy in place, endorsed by leadership and periodically updated?	2 - There are some defined strategies around environmental sustainability in some of our institutes.	Formalise leadership endorsement of the strategy and ensure it includes a mechanism for periodic updates. Begin integrating it into RI-level decision-making.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Are roles and responsibilities for environmental sustainability clearly assigned across relevant functions within the RI?	2 - According to the survey that was done in EGI ACE project, some roles and responsibilities were defined in some of our institutes.	Document the assigned responsibilities formally (e.g. in organisational charts, role descriptions, quality systems) and ensure they are communicated internally.	Medium improvement priority	Low effort required	Urgent implementation priority
To what extent is environmental sustainability integrated into the RI's internal policies, management systems, or quality frameworks?	1 - Only 2 out of 15 institutes that filled in the GreenDIGIT Survey mentioned about the policies.	Review existing policies, management systems, and quality frameworks to identify where environmental sustainability is absent. Begin drafting updates or addenda that reflect sustainability considerations.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Does the RI include environmental sustainability criteria in procurement processes and supplier evaluations?	3 - Majority of our institutes follow green procurement processes and take sustainability into account during procurement.	No action needed. Maintain criteria updates and consider supplier engagement strategies to support continuous sustainability improvement.	Low improvement priority	High effort required	No Action Needed
Stakeholder Engagement and Awareness					
To what extent does the RI provide staff training or awareness programmes on environmental sustainability topics relevant to their roles?	2 - Around half of our institutes run trainings around sustainability topics.	Establish structured training programmes with role-specific content. Include periodic refreshers and track staff participation and feedback.	Medium improvement priority	High effort required	Low implementation priority
Are relevant stakeholders (e.g. users, suppliers, partners) engaged in environmental planning or sustainability goal-setting processes?	1 - There is not enough evidence about involving stakeholders in environmental topics.	Identify key stakeholder groups and initiate basic engagement on environmental topics (e.g. surveys, meetings, informal consultations).	High improvement priority	High effort required	Planned implementation priority

Does the RI regularly communicate its environmental performance, actions, or goals to internal and external stakeholders?	2 - Some of our institutes share their sustainability reports on their websites.	Identify key performance metrics and develop internal channels for sharing environmental information (e.g. newsletters, intranet updates).	Medium improvement priority	Low effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Energy Efficiency and Decarbonisation					
What proportion of the RI's energy consumption is sourced from renewable energy, and how is this verified?	2 - Some of our institutes use and track renewable energy sources.	Increase the share of renewable energy through updated contracts or on-site generation. Implement processes for regular verification and reporting (e.g. through Guarantees of Origin, utility audits).	Medium improvement priority	High effort required	Low implementation priority
Are AI or automation systems used to optimise energy consumption across compute, cooling, or other infrastructure components?	1 - Only a few of our institutes are optimising automated workflows in certain actions to minimise energy consumption. Not known if AI is used for this purpose.	Identify infrastructure areas with high energy use and evaluate the potential of AI or automation tools for energy optimisation. Initiate pilot projects or feasibility assessments.	High improvement priority	High effort required	Planned implementation priority
Does the RI implement strategies to recover or reuse waste heat generated by infrastructure?	2 - Some of our institutes utilise waste heat reuse methods.	Implement basic heat recovery systems where feasible. Monitor effectiveness and explore opportunities to expand reuse or integrate with external systems.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Is the RI's PUE monitored regularly, and are efforts in place to optimise it over time?	2 - Plenty of our institutes calculate, track, and benchmark their PUE but it's still open for improvements.	Establish routine monitoring of PUE and identify areas where efficiency can be improved (e.g. cooling systems, power distribution). Set internal targets for optimisation.	Medium improvement priority	Low effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Is CUE calculated and used as a metric for assessing carbon performance of the RI's operations?	1 - Majority of our institutes do not calculate CUE or use this value in their decision making.	Familiarise the team with Carbon Usage Effectiveness (CUE) and assess whether sufficient data exists to begin basic calculations. Identify carbon-intensive operational areas.	High improvement priority	Low effort required	Immediate implementation priority
Does the RI participate in energy flexibility initiatives,	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope

such as demand response or smart grid integration?					
Environmental Monitoring and Impact					
Which environmental KPIs (e.g. GHG emissions, energy, water, waste) are currently measured and how frequently are they reported?	2 - Some of our institutes measure and report environmental KPIS.	Expand KPI measurement to cover multiple impact areas (e.g. GHG, energy, water, waste). Establish consistent reporting processes and assign responsibilities.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
To what extent are environmental metrics integrated into the RI's strategic planning or operational decision-making?	2 - Some of our institutes use environmental KPIs in their decision making by adding them into their short- and long-term goals.	Incorporate environmental metrics into key strategic documents, project evaluations, or budget planning. Ensure decision-makers have access to relevant data during planning cycles.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Has the RI conducted or applied lifecycle assessments (LCA) to evaluate its environmental impact across different phases, including monitoring of Global Warming Potential (GWP) and Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)?	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope
Is WUE or any comparable metric tracked and used to assess the RI's water efficiency performance?	1 - Majority of our institutes do not calculate WUE.	Review current water usage practices and assess the feasibility of applying Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE) or a comparable metric. Begin collecting relevant data where possible.	Medium improvement priority	Low effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Are dedicated tools or platforms in place for tracking, visualising, or reporting environmental performance?	1 - Majority of our institutes do not have a dedicated environmental monitoring tools or we don't have any evidence of it.	Identify suitable tools or platforms for environmental data tracking and reporting. Evaluate whether existing systems (e.g. monitoring software, spreadsheets) meet reporting needs.	High improvement priority	Low effort required	Immediate implementation priority
Pollution, Waste, and Circularity					

Are practices in place to reduce operational waste generation, including e-waste from IT systems and equipment?	1 - There is not enough evidence about waste reduction practices across our institutes.	Identify main sources of operational and e-waste. Begin implementing basic waste reduction measures (e.g. paperless processes, proper e-waste disposal procedures).	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Does the RI apply defined procedures for the reuse, recycling, or proper disposal of decommissioned equipment?	3 - Majority of our institutes have regulations around recycling and reusing equipment.	No action needed. Maintain procedures and consider auditing or reporting results to enhance transparency and continuous improvement.	Low improvement priority	High effort required	No Action Needed
Are circular IT principles such as reuse, modularity, or refurbishment applied in procurement or infrastructure management?	1 - Majority of our institutes do not consider circularity criteria during the design/procurement phase or there is not enough evidence of it.	Review procurement and infrastructure policies to identify opportunities to apply circular IT principles (e.g. reuse, modular design, refurbishment). Begin piloting circular approaches in select areas.	High improvement priority	Low effort required	Immediate implementation priority
Are measures in place to monitor and manage pollution risks related to air, water, or soil emissions from RI operations?	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope
Are environmental criteria applied when selecting materials or products, with preference for low-impact or non-toxic options?	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope
Water and Ecosystems					
To what extent does the RI monitor its water consumption and implement strategies to reduce it?	1 - Majority of our institutes either don't monitor the water usage or do not have any reduction plans.	Begin monitoring water usage across relevant operations. Identify key consumption points and explore opportunities for reduction (e.g. fixture upgrades, behavioural campaigns).	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Does the RI assess and manage its potential impacts on local ecosystems or biodiversity, particularly for physical infrastructure?	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope

Are there systems or practices in place for rainwater harvesting, water reuse, or managing stormwater run-off?	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope	Not in Scope
Does the RI use water-based cooling systems, and are measures in place to optimise their water efficiency and minimise environmental impact?	2 - The institutes that utilises water cooling systems do follow relevant actions such as monitoring and improving efficiency. There is not enough evidence about reducing water use.	Implement water-saving strategies such as evaporative cooling optimisation, water reuse, or integration of hybrid cooling. Document performance and begin setting reduction goals.	Medium improvement priority	High effort required	Low implementation priority
Lifecycle Integration					
To what extent are sustainability considerations integrated into the design and planning of new infrastructure or services?	2 - Sustainability is considered in some of our institutions during the design phase.	Embed defined sustainability criteria into design frameworks, including materials selection, energy efficiency, and end-of-life considerations. Document decisions and outcomes.	Medium improvement priority	Medium effort required	Planned implementation priority
Are sustainability criteria applied during the implementation or deployment of infrastructure components and systems?	2 - Sustainability is considered in some of our institutions during the deployment/implementation phase.	Formalise sustainability criteria within procurement and deployment procedures. Monitor compliance and document implementation outcomes.	Medium improvement priority	Low effort required	Urgent implementation priority
What sustainability practices are in place for the operation and maintenance of the RI's infrastructure and services?	2 - Some of our institutes tick all the boxes but majority of them follow limited actions during operations phase.	Implement structured sustainability practices into operations and maintenance (e.g. energy tracking, green cleaning protocols, lifecycle extension). Monitor effectiveness and adjust as needed.	Medium improvement priority	High effort required	Low implementation priority
Does the RI include environmental considerations in its decommissioning or termination plans for infrastructure or services?	3 - Majority of our institutes have green decommissioning protocols in place during termination phase.	No action needed. Maintain current decommissioning protocols and review periodically for alignment with best practices and emerging requirements.	Low improvement priority	High effort required	No Action Needed

7.4 RI 4 Use case – SLICES

Table 20: SLICES RI use case overview.

Question	Self-assessment score (1-2-3)	Recommended Action	Improvement Priority	Effort Required	Implementation Priority
Governance and Compliance					
To what extent is the RI aligned with relevant EU environmental regulations such as CSRD, ESRS, EED, ESPR, WEEE, LCA, ISO14040, ISO14044?	1 - SLICES is in stage of preparation and partly pre-operation stage	Conduct a regulatory gap analysis to identify which EU environmental regulations apply and where the RI is currently non-compliant. Engage legal or compliance expertise to support interpretation if needed.	High improvement priority	High effort required	Planned implementation priority
Has the RI conducted a review or gap analysis to identify which regulations apply and how they are addressed?	1 - SLICES is in stage of preparation and partly pre-operation stage. Analysis not yet conducted.	Initiate a structured regulatory review to identify applicable EU regulations (e.g. CSRD, ESRS, EED, ESPR, WEEE). Engage relevant internal or external expertise and document initial findings.	High improvement priority	High effort required	Planned implementation priority
Is there a documented environmental sustainability strategy in place, endorsed by leadership and periodically updated?	1 - SLICES is in stage of preparation and partly pre-operation stage	Draft a documented environmental sustainability strategy that outlines goals, scope, and key priorities. Secure leadership engagement to initiate endorsement.	High improvement priority	Low effort required	Immediate implementation priority
Are roles and responsibilities for environmental sustainability clearly assigned across relevant functions within the RI?	1 - No roles for Environmental sustainability strategy established	Identify key functions and assign clear responsibilities for environmental sustainability. Ensure responsibility is not siloed but shared across operational and strategic roles.	High improvement priority	Low effort required	Immediate implementation priority

To what extent is environmental sustainability integrated into the RI's internal policies, management systems, or quality frameworks?	1 - Environmental sustainability policy is defined as a general commitment. No detailed compliance specified.	To what extent is environmental sustainability integrated into the RI's internal policies, management systems, or quality frameworks?	High improvement priority	High effort required	Planned implementation priority
Does the RI include environmental sustainability criteria in procurement processes and supplier evaluations?	1 - Procurement policy is not defined	Begin integrating basic environmental sustainability criteria into procurement guidelines and supplier selection processes. Reference relevant standards (e.g. EU Green Public Procurement) where applicable.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Stakeholder Engagement and Awareness					
To what extent does the RI provide staff training or awareness programmes on environmental sustainability topics relevant to their roles?	2 - Sustainability training is included in the SLICES-RI meetings and tutorials	Develop and deliver basic sustainability awareness sessions for staff. Tailor content to general operational relevance and RI objectives.	Medium improvement priority	Low effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Are relevant stakeholders (e.g. users, suppliers, partners) engaged in environmental planning or sustainability goal-setting processes?	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope
Does the RI regularly communicate its environmental performance, actions, or goals to internal and external stakeholders?	2 - Communication and discussion about including Environmental Sustainability aspects into SLICES-RI design and operations has started in Working Groups	Identify key performance metrics and develop internal channels for sharing environmental information (e.g. newsletters, intranet updates).	Medium improvement priority	Low effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Energy Efficiency and Decarbonisation					
What proportion of the RI's energy consumption is sourced from	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope

renewable energy, and how is this verified?					
Are AI or automation systems used to optimise energy consumption across compute, cooling, or other infrastructure components?	2 - AI/ML based energy monitoring and optimisation is a part of individual testbeds operation.	Identify infrastructure areas with high energy use and evaluate the potential of AI or automation tools for energy optimisation. Initiate pilot projects or feasibility assessments.	Medium improvement priority	High effort required	Low implementation priority
Does the RI implement strategies to recover or reuse waste heat generated by infrastructure?	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope
Is the RI's PUE monitored regularly, and are efforts in place to optimise it over time?	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope
Is CUE calculated and used as a metric for assessing carbon performance of the RI's operations?	1 - CUE calculation is included in some experiments run on individual testbeds operation.	Familiarise the team with Carbon Usage Effectiveness (CUE) and assess whether sufficient data exists to begin basic calculations. Identify carbon-intensive operational areas.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Does the RI participate in energy flexibility initiatives, such as demand response or smart grid integration?	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope
Environmental Monitoring and Impact					
Which environmental KPIs (e.g. GHG emissions, energy, water, waste) are currently measured and how frequently are they reported?	1 - KPIs are not measured at this stage. Measuring and reporting KPI and environmental metrics will be developed at the next stage to comply with ESFRI RM2026 requirements.	Identify key environmental KPIs relevant to RI operations. Begin collecting basic data on at least one dimension (e.g. energy use or waste generation) and define a reporting cadence.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority

To what extent are environmental metrics integrated into the RI's strategic planning or operational decision-making?	1 - KPIs are not measured at this stage. Measuring and reporting KPI and environmental metrics will be developed at the next stage to comply with ESFRI RM2026 requirements.	Identify opportunities to integrate basic environmental metrics (e.g. energy use, GHG emissions) into routine planning or procurement decisions. Raise awareness among decision-makers.	High improvement priority	High effort required	Planned implementation priority
Has the RI conducted or applied lifecycle assessments (LCA) to evaluate its environmental impact across different phases, including monitoring of Global Warming Potential (GWP) and Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)?	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope
Is WUE or any comparable metric tracked and used to assess the RI's water efficiency performance?	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope
Are dedicated tools or platforms in place for tracking, visualising, or reporting environmental performance?	1 - Environment Monitoring system/tools are not available but will be developed at the next stage to comply with ESFRI RM2026 requirements.	Identify suitable tools or platforms for environmental data tracking and reporting. Evaluate whether existing systems (e.g. monitoring software, spreadsheets) meet reporting needs.	High improvement priority	High effort required	Planned implementation priority
Pollution, Waste, and Circularity					
Are practices in place to reduce operational waste generation, including e-waste from IT systems and equipment?	1 - Reduction of operational waste or end-of-life equipment will be developed at the next stage of deploying RI for operation.	Identify main sources of operational and e-waste. Begin implementing basic waste reduction measures (e.g. paperless processes, proper e-waste disposal procedures).	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Does the RI apply defined procedures for the reuse, recycling, or proper disposal of decommissioned equipment?	1 - Reduction of operational waste or end-of-life equipment will be developed at the next stage of deploying RI for operation.	Develop and document procedures for the proper reuse, recycling, or disposal of decommissioned equipment, in compliance with WEEE or relevant regulations.	High improvement priority	High effort required	Planned implementation priority

Are circular IT principles such as reuse, modularity, or refurbishment applied in procurement or infrastructure management?	1 - Reduction of operational waste or end-of-life equipment will be developed at the next stage of deploying RI for operation.	Review procurement and infrastructure policies to identify opportunities to apply circular IT principles (e.g. reuse, modular design, refurbishment). Begin piloting circular approaches in select areas.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
Are measures in place to monitor and manage pollution risks related to air, water, or soil emissions from RI operations?	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope
Are environmental criteria applied when selecting materials or products, with preference for low-impact or non-toxic options?	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope
Water and Ecosystems					
To what extent does the RI monitor its water consumption and implement strategies to reduce it?	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope
Does the RI assess and manage its potential impacts on local ecosystems or biodiversity, particularly for physical infrastructure?	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope
Are there systems or practices in place for rainwater harvesting, water reuse, or managing stormwater runoff?	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope
Does the RI use water-based cooling systems, and are measures in	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope	Not in scope

place to optimise their water efficiency and minimise environmental impact?					
Lifecycle Integration					
To what extent are sustainability considerations integrated into the design and planning of new infrastructure or services?	1 - Sustainability will be embedded in the design of new services using GreenDIGIT recommendations.	Introduce sustainability checkpoints into design and planning processes. Begin referencing basic sustainability principles or guidelines during early-stage decision-making.	High improvement priority	Low effort required	Immediate implementation priority
Are sustainability criteria applied during the implementation or deployment of infrastructure components and systems?	1 - Sustainability aspects will be considered during the implementation stage, using GreenDIGIT recommendations.	Identify implementation phases where sustainability can be applied (e.g. material sourcing, vendor selection, construction). Begin including basic criteria in execution checklists.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority
What sustainability practices are in place for the operation and maintenance of the RI's infrastructure and services?	1 - Environmental Sustainability practices (including metrics, monitoring, reporting) will be implemented during the operation stage, using GreenDIGIT recommendations.	Identify operational areas where sustainability practices can be introduced (e.g. energy management, resource efficiency, preventive maintenance). Begin applying basic principles.	High improvement priority	High effort required	Planned implementation priority
Does the RI include environmental considerations in its decommissioning or termination plans for infrastructure or services?	1 - Current decommissioning policy doesn't address environmental aspects. Decommissioning/ termination phase will be extended with environmental and circular economy aspects/ practices.	Review existing decommissioning or termination procedures and identify gaps related to environmental impact (e.g. equipment disposal, site remediation). Draft basic guidelines for responsible end-of-life practices.	High improvement priority	Medium effort required	Urgent implementation priority

8 Guidelines and recommendations for the RI lifecycle

This section presents a comprehensive set of guidelines and recommendations for the Research Infrastructure (RI) lifecycle, spanning from concept development to termination. Developed as part of Task T3.3, these guidelines are intended to support RIs at each stage by providing in-depth recommendations that complement the environmental impact assessment, ensuring more sustainable and responsible practices throughout the lifecycle. The guidelines are compatible with recommendations emerging from the Research Infrastructure Lifecycle Model reported in Deliverable **D4.2** [9] and Whitepaper [10].

8.1 Concept development

The integration of environmental and energy sustainability considerations at the earliest stages of a RI is critical for ensuring long-term climate resilience and alignment with the European sustainability goals. In the concept development phase, there is a strategic opportunity to highly affect the RI's future performance alongside with its energy sustainability goals. The following sub-sections highlight the foundational steps for achieving these goals.

8.1.1 Purpose of concept development in the RI lifecycle

In this phase, the foundational period is given for the RI, where high-level conceptual visions are translated into initial structures and strategic directions. It is worth noting that, from an environmental standpoint, this phase represents the earliest, as well as a great opportunity to influence positively and achieve the long-term sustainability goals. By integrating holistically ecological considerations at the start, RIs may avoid unsustainable practices which lead to negative environmental impact. The major goal at this point is to build flexibility, accountability, and alignment with the European Green Deal's [15] goals of climate neutrality and circularity.

8.1.2 Setting an environmental sustainability strategy and goals

During this phase, RIs should define clear and ambitious environmental sustainability goals. It is recommended that as a first step, the RI should draft an environmental sustainability strategy or policy to identify clear roles and responsibilities for the managers in charge of sustainability planning and practices. GreenDIGIT Deliverable **D8.2 “First Policy Recommendations”** [16] offers detailed recommendations to help RIs set internal RI policies.

The goals set in the sustainability strategy should be aligned with the European Commission's Green Deal targets, such as achieving net-zero GHG emissions by 2050 [17]. More specifically, during this phase it is essential for the RI developers to:

- Establish environmental KPIs.
- Incorporate climate adaptation and mitigation strategies
- Identify long-term opportunities for positive environmental contributions.

It is essential for all the goals stated to be transparent, measurable and can be revisited, as the RI evolves.

8.1.3 Early environmental scoping

At this point, and after defining the concept and the general sustainability strategy and goals of the RI, a preliminary scan of environmental effects can be performed. Thus, the potential environmental impacts will be assessed, even only high-level estimates can be exported at this specific phase of the RI. This preliminary scan can include:

- Mapping the lifecycle of core infrastructure components;
- Identifying high-impact phases;
- Estimating emissions, energy use, and waste generation;
- Re-evaluating alternatives that offer environmental benefits compared to selected approaches, techniques, etc.

8.1.4 Stakeholder engagement and strategic alignment

Furthermore, stakeholder engagement should be initiated early for the RI. The inclusion of diverse perspectives and priorities can be achieved, through the involvement of a large variety of stakeholders (environmental experts, users, engineers, policy makers etc.). Other than that, additional activities to ensure that strategic alignment will be achieved at the RI may include:

- Hosting co-design workshops (with focus on sustainability themes);
- Establishing governance structures that embed environmental directions (e.g., sustainability advisory boards);
- Ensuring strategic alignment with institutional and national sustainability agendas, as well as pan-European frameworks like the ESFRI Roadmap.

8.2 Design

Following the concept development phase, the design phase of a RI is also pivotal for shaping its long-term environmental goals and footprint. The decisions made at this stage, have far and long-term impact for resource efficiency, emissions, operational performance and finally end-of-life sustainability. This phase provides fertile ground for aligning with EU Green Deal objectives and sets the stage for measurable environmental performance. As emphasised in GreenDIGIT Deliverable **D4.2 “Architecture Definition, Lifecycle Model and Requirements Specification for Sustainable RI”** [9], embedding sustainability by design ensures that environmental objectives are built intrinsically into the system’s core, thus promoting the compliance with EU Green Deal objectives.

8.2.1 Role of design in environmental performance

Initially, design can be the most impactful stage in determining an RI’s ecological footprint throughout its lifecycle. Each architectural and technical choice and component from top to bottom affects GHG emissions, energy demands and resource utilisation. According to GreenDIGIT Deliverable **D4.2** [9], a layered and modular architecture enhances flexibility, enables targeted optimisations, and supports energy-aware orchestration. Thus, sustainable principles from this phase may lead to:

- Lower lifecycle emissions (efficient layout and resource planning);
- Improve energy efficiency (through both passive and active energy saving choices);
- Support digital transition by integrating green ICT systems (servers, edge computing etc.).

8.2.2 Sustainable infrastructure and ICT design strategies

The selection of proper strategies at this stage ensures a future proof RI and typically include adaptability, resilience, and resource efficiency. The adoption of modular components that can be easily replaced or upgraded is highly proposed for a modern sustainable RI. Such modularity (**D4.2** Pillar 1 [9])

allows targeted sustainability improvements at different layers of the infrastructure, from data centres to user interfaces. Some indicative strategies are listed below:

- Utilisation of low impact circular materials;
- Implementation of bioclimatic design principles;
- Design within green ICT principles in mind.

These design actions enable alignment with lifecycle sustainability goals and the ESFRI Roadmap sustainability recommendations. It is worth noting that these and additional strategies can also be found in Deliverable **D3.1 “RIs Landscape review, best practices analysis and identification of needs within the ESFRI RIs”** [\[1\]](#).

8.2.3 Energy and resource efficiency

Furthermore, energy and resource efficiency are critical throughout the RI’s design phase. Proper decisions taken at this stage may reduce the RI’s operational costs and reduce the environmental footprint from day one. For that to be achieved, the following guidelines are given:

1. **Use less - reduce energy and resource consumption:**
 - Implement ISO 50001-2018 compliant energy management systems to monitor and optimise energy use;
 - Use energy-optimised software and workflows (especially for HPC and data intensive applications);
 - Minimise transport-related emissions by reducing business travel and supporting hybrid work models;
 - Leverage natural site advantages (e.g. locating data centres in cooler climates or underground to reduce cooling loads).
2. **Use renewable energy sources:**
 - Procure electricity from certified green energy suppliers or install and use on-site renewable systems (e.g., solar PV, wind).
3. **Reuse and recycle - apply circular economy principles:**
 - Comply with WEEE Directive (proper electronic waste handling and recycling).
 - Use modular hardware designs.
 - Implement repair policies and internal reuse platforms for components, paper, plastic, etc.
4. **Shared infrastructures - promote efficiency and collaboration:**
 - Use federated RI platforms (e.g., EOSC, EGI, PRACE) to avoid duplication and scale energy efficiency.
 - Promote shared facility planning to optimise infrastructure use, aligned with Pillar 1 of GreenDIGIT Deliverable **D4.2** [\[9\]](#).
5. **Educate and innovate - Build a culture of sustainability:**
 - Deliver training on ISO standards (50001, 14001) and sustainability KPIs to technical and administrative staff.
 - Use visual dashboards and user portals to display energy use and sustainability impacts and motivate the personnel.
6. **Set KPIs, measure and improve - enable continuous monitoring and optimisation:**
 - Implement a multi-layer observability infrastructure, as proposed at GreenDIGIT **D4.2** Pillar 4 [\[9\]](#).
 - Use standardised KPIs like:
 - PUE (ISO 30134-2) – Power Usage Effectiveness
 - CUE (ISO 30134-8) – Carbon Usage Effectiveness
 - WUE (ISO 30134-9) – Water Usage Effectiveness

8.2.4 End-of-Life and circularity by design

An important phase beyond RI operation is the end of life. A proper planning will ensure that the components, systems and materials are recoverable, reusable or recyclable. A key principle which is also analysed in Deliverable **D4.2** (Lifecycle-Oriented Sustainability), which emphasises on embedding sustainability throughout the entire RI lifecycle [9]. In accordance with ISO 14001 and WEEE Directive, end-of-life should be designed to support circularity and material recovery. This involves:

- Integration of the LCA;
- Use of non-toxic, recyclable, and sustainably sourced materials (ISO 14040/44 Lifecycle Assessment);
- Design of modular assemblies;
- Design for Disassembly.

8.2.5 Monitoring readiness and KPIs

Finally, during the design phase it is very critical to support monitoring readiness at the RI. This will provide the ability to report, which leads to long-term optimisation. Furthermore, it is vital to build into infrastructure observability from the start, as also emphasised in Deliverable **D4.2** (Pillar 4) [9].

8.3 Preparation

The preparation phase aims to transform the concept and design phases that have shaped the strategic vision particularly in terms of environmental impact management into a concrete, operational action plan. It is, therefore, essential that the level of attention and resources allocated to this stage in the lifecycle of the RI are in line with the challenges and objectives defined above. This is because it includes not only the structuring of funding and the development of legal and administrative frameworks, but also the building of working groups, operational roadmap and the development of prototypes. All of this must be aligned with the goals and vision defined in the concept development step.

8.3.1 Finalisation of the financial and partnership agreements

This phase includes finalising the financing plans, which requires particular attention to the costs associated to environmental impact management. Improving the environmental performance of a research infrastructure can have significant financial consequences. For example, the purchase of energy-efficient hardware, the use of renewable energy or the ISO standards certification can increase the budget of the RI. On the other hand, controlling energy costs and the possibility of obtaining new types of financing, thanks to a virtuous environmental approach, can have a positive impact on this budget. In addition, the preparation includes at least two types of partnership agreements:

- With the project stakeholder, formalising their participation and commitment to the RI policy (see next section);
- With subcontractors and suppliers, in particular those for access to shared resources (data centres or computing and storage infrastructures), for the procurement or recycling of hardware or for the supply of renewable energy.

8.3.2 Definition of policies

Drawing up a general policy in line with environmental standards is essential but can be complex in practice. This policy, required by ISO 50001 and ISO 14001, forms the basis for all internal procedures and gives concrete expression to the objectives defined in the previous sections of this chapter. It should also take into account the environmental commitments and policies of stakeholders. Implementing a policy that conflicts with, or ignores, these existing frameworks risks disengagement of some

RI participants. However, this does not preclude setting ambitious targets and even having positive influence on stakeholders' future policies.

The policy will help the RI steering committee in making both administrative and operational decisions in line with the defined environmental objectives. It should be referenced in the agreements detailed in the previous section. For example, it can specify procedures for managing the equipment's end-of-life or rules for sourcing renewable energy. This policy may be completed by others, such as a policy on CSR. So, ethical aspects of RI could be addressed, particularly when accessing resources that may affect local populations (i.e. water use or the disposal of IT waste).

Lastly, this section should define the roadmap for obtaining RI certification in line with the international standards (such as ISO 50001:2018 and ISO 14001) identified in the previous phases.

8.3.3 Structuration of the organisation

The organisational objective is threefold. First, setting up the overall governance and building the first teams is an important part of the preparation phase. For example, team member profiles should have awareness of environmental challenges. The operational management could include experts that are able to manage thought-out modular architecture. Such architecture would permit to adapt the technical capacities of the RI (digital infrastructures, equipment, networks) to real needs, avoiding unnecessary oversizing and encouraging the reuse or reallocation of resources in case of scientific need changes. The organisation of the RI should also include:

- A communications planning to promote activities linked to the management of environmental impacts;
- A training plan for supporting the teams in achieving their environmental impact management objectives. This is the key to success of the future application of best practice in energy management, purchase optimisation or developing pertinent metrology tools.

Secondly, the structuring of management support tools is equally important. The RI governance must integrate the monitoring of performance indicators and ensure continuous improvement through a dedicated dashboard, directly linked to the overall strategy. These indicators, defined in the previous stages, can be refined during this phase. This phase should also include an initial measurement of the various indicators, in order to assess their relevance and act as a sort of '0' point. This measurement will make it possible to diagnose the hot spot and identify the most environmentally advantageous actions to be taken during the implementation phase.

It will also help to define the policies described in section 8.2.2. Such indicators may include metrics related to energy consumption, CO₂ emissions or the share of used renewable resources. It is also important to plan correction actions to be taken if the case of the deviation from any of these indicators occurs. Implementing a robust metrology plan will increase the credibility to the overall approach, whether in the eyes of stakeholders, RI users and funders.

Thirdly, this section must also cover technical deployment planning. It is driven by both the scientific and environmental objectives of the RI. It may, for example, include the selection of appropriate instrumentation for monitoring key metrics, and drafting environmental and social clauses for calls for tender. If some information is missing to finalise the planning or the previously defined policies, this phase can be completed by a prototyping stage.

8.3.4 Production of prototypes

Finally, the preparation phase can include the design and testing of prototypes, such as the assessment of grid power services or testing new instrumentation for specific metric monitoring. The prototyping phase not only makes it possible to validate additional metrics, but also to support the achievement of more ambitious environmental impact management objectives.

8.3.5 Deliverables

The preparation phase results in a set of concrete deliverables, representing the operational commitment of the research infrastructure:

- Signed contracts and partnership agreements;
- Detailed implementation plan aligned with sustainability policy;
- Validated organisational structure and governance;
- Eventually, the first prototypes or demonstrators.

These elements form a solid basis for moving on to the next phase during which the technical and organisational solutions will be implemented in accordance with the environmental impact management strategy. They enable also the use of well-tested solutions and realistic environmental performance targets.

8.4 Implementation

The main objective of the implementation phase is to put in place sustainable and energy efficient services based on the architectural framework and the identified specific conditions. The architecture concepts and lifecycle model are described in Deliverable **D4.2** [9].

Ensure green principles and flexibility on all layers: select equipment, implement APIs, services and tools for scientific workflows with sustainability in mind. Design services and their features flexibly so that late identified needs and necessary changes based on scientific workflows can be implemented in an energy efficient manner. Create conditions for optimising applications and scientific software and **re-engineering of scientific workflows**. Prefer modular systems that can be upgraded or expanded without significant environmental disruption, reducing the need for future resource-intensive retrofits.

Implement services as power grid aware and tune its behaviour based on specific conditions and environment. Gather information about the energetic infrastructure of RI, main power grid connection capacity, fraction of data centre in total RI power consumption, other technologies and its demands (cooling, experiments). Important are specific conditions like current and possible usage of waste heat or constrains agreed with electricity supplier.

Set the objectives for optimisation. Possibilities:

- Optimise for carbon impact (lower power consumption when carbon intensity is high), set the maximum allowed reduction of HW usage;
- Optimise for price (lower power consumption where the electricity price is high), set the maximum allowed reduction of HW usage;
- Optimise for consumption profile - reduce computing power consumption based on other technologies in the same building/campus (one connection point to the electrical grid with agreement about consumption profile)

Ensure monitoring readiness, implement a multi-layer observability infrastructure to continuously track and report sustainability metrics. Collect and transparently show the contribution of individual layers, components and user tasks to these metrics. Prepare regular evaluation process.

Prepare appropriate technical and organisational documentation covering the architecture, components and their settings, typical workflows, expected procedures for scaling and troubleshooting. Customise training and education materials and courses, implement an awareness campaign for administrators and end users.

Identify and assess the impacts of implemented green measures on related subsystems. For example, there may be increased calculation time, slow data transfers or other parameters that need to be taken into account (e.g. wall time adjustment in the batch system).

8.5 Operation

The operation phase involves the continuous optimisation of all aspects of operation, providing services for research activities while maintaining efficiency, security, and sustainability. Focusing on sustainability aspects means working with all operational aspects and looking for potential savings in each of them.

Continuous monitoring and optimisation are based on real-time observability infrastructure mentioned above and combination of performance and green metrics. Thanks to compatibility with existing infrastructures like EGI and its capabilities (monitoring, resource management, evaluation process) the process can be very transparent and use emerging technologies with newly gained knowledge. Optimisation should be connected through all layers, from application developers to collaboration with the technical management of data centres.

Power grid aware computing is a practice where RI operations are adjusted to be in line with the current state of the power grid. This is part of the smart-grid concept [18], where the most important is the ability to provide flexibility. Flexibility is one of the solutions to the energy and climate challenge [19]. There are two main scenarios:

- **Providing RI flexibility as an asset** for the Transmission System Operator (TSO) of the electricity power grid. In this case, the RI responds to TSO signals (frequency regulation and generation-consumption balance regulation). TSO turns the ability to control RI consumption turns into stability, resilience and resource conservation in the power grid. At the same time, this reduces the carbon footprint.
- **Using the ability to manage consumption to lower carbon footprint by RI itself.** In that case the RI is using data about online or expected carbon intensity of electricity mix to shift its consumption to the times with lower carbon intensity of regional electricity. The advantage is the possibility of implementation without connection to the TSO regulation service if this is limited to large power consumers only.

Flexibility can be technically implemented as **load shifting** by slowing down or delaying the execution of computational tasks. This can be achieved for fully loaded compute nodes by reducing the maximum frequency of the CPU and GPU. The second option is to **optimise the scheduling of jobs** based on their properties, especially their computational complexity (CPU intensity). This cannot achieve the response times of minutes needed for the smart grid but can reduce the carbon impact without significantly increasing the runtime of jobs and thus the unwanted impact on embedded carbon.

Assessment and evaluation of the power grid aware computing measures. Impact assessment can take place at several levels and with different precision. The proposed method is to correlate the power consumption pattern of computing nodes at the site-wide level with the carbon intensity pattern of regional electricity. The correlation should significantly change before and after applying the measures. Note that CPU load metric cannot be used because it is not meaningful in case of changing CPU frequencies.

8.6 Termination

The termination phase of a Research Infrastructure (RI), particularly within digital ecosystems, constitutes a crucial stage of the lifecycle that requires systematic environmental consideration. Integrating termination planning into the overall sustainability strategy from the early stages of a RI's design enables more accurate lifecycle assessments and facilitates smoother, lower-impact closures.

Termination also has implications for Scope 3 emissions. Since the embodied carbon of the infrastructure becomes locked in during construction and production, it cannot be significantly reduced after implementation. Extending the operational lifetime of a RI amortizes these emissions over a longer period, whereas premature termination results in a higher embodied carbon footprint per unit of scientific output.

Causes of termination may be given by many factors, such as by obsolescence, lack of funding, scientific irrelevance, safety concerns, or the completion of the infrastructure's mission. While often under-represented in traditional impact assessments, this phase entails activities such as infrastructure decommissioning, data migration or deletion, hardware dismantling, and land reclamation, which carry potential environmental consequences. Termination phase could also mean re-orientation of RI sites, e.g. nuclear research sites or high-energy physics, where outdated RI have been transformed into analytical facilities with new science missions built upon the presence of technological infrastructure, logistics, human resources and organisation [5, 20].

Properly addressing RI termination helps ensure the responsible management of resources and the minimisation of residual environmental burdens. Key environmental impacts include the generation of electronic waste (e-waste), emissions associated with final data handling and migration processes, and the embodied energy losses related to the premature disposal of components. Social and operational dimensions (i.e. the disruption to user communities or research continuity) must also be acknowledged and mitigated through structured planning.

In the context of lifecycle inventory preparation, the following elements should be specifically considered for the termination phase:

- **Responsible disposal planning:** including e-waste handling in line with environmental regulations and circular economy principles, in compliance with national and international safety regulations and environmental standards.
- **Data decommissioning:** ensuring secure, low-energy data deletion or transfer to long-term archival repositories.
- **Hardware deconstruction and recycling:** prioritising reuse, refurbishment, or material recovery to minimise landfill contribution.
- **Scientific community continuity:** assessing the downstream effects of RI closure on dependent research ecosystems.
- **Financial and legal planning:** Review and settle contracts, grants, and service agreements and address liabilities, such as site restoration.

Environmental indicators for this phase may include device recyclability ratios, residual carbon footprint from dismantling logistics, and energy consumption of end-of-life data operations.

If termination of RIs cannot be avoided, planning ahead and strategic decision-making are crucial in order to be more sustainable and less impactful. Some practical guidelines that can be used for careful planning are [21]:

- (a) **Impact on scientific community:** The termination should be managed to minimise disruption to users of the infrastructure and researchers.
- (b) **Responsible disposal:** Pre-planning responsible disposal of assets and equipment is crucial during termination
- (c) **Decommissioning:** In case of decommissioning of the infrastructure, a plan for dismantling and removing equipment or facilities is required.

9 Conclusion

This deliverable has developed and validated a comprehensive environmental impact assessment methodology and accompanying guidelines tailored for digital Research Infrastructures within the GreenDIGIT project. The methodology provides a robust framework for assessing the stage of environmental sustainability of RIs, focusing on key dimensions, including carbon emissions, energy and water consumption, and waste management across the RI lifecycle.

The approach integrates established frameworks including the ESFRI Lifecycle Approach, Lifecycle Assessment principles, IAM4SDG structural support, and Environmental, Social, and Governance considerations, ensuring alignment with relevant industry standards and the evolving ESFRI roadmap towards 2026. Through its application and testing in real-world operational environments of four participating RIs (EGI, SLICES, SoBigData, and EBRAINS), the methodology has demonstrated its practical applicability and reliability.

Key outputs include customised environmental impact reports for the participating RIs, which reveal actionable insights into their environmental performance and identify targeted strategic recommendations for impact reduction. These outputs directly support the verification of GreenDIGIT Objective 1 to assess the status of environmental impact of the participating RIs. The methodology and self-assessment questionnaire lay a solid foundation for the development of a greenRI certification scheme and wider adoption of sustainable practices across the European Research Infrastructure community, to be worked on in later GreenDIGIT Work Packages.

The framework and guidelines established in this deliverable will inform subsequent project activities aimed at refining environmental monitoring, broadening engagement with digital service providers, and promoting systemic transformation towards sustainability in the DIGIT domain. This report marks a critical step in enabling research infrastructures to embrace environmental responsibility and contribute to the European Green Deal's objectives for a sustainable digital future.

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Appendix A. Examples of environmental impact categories and indicators from ITU-T L. 1410 [\[9\]](#)

Table 5 – Examples of environmental impact categories and indicators

Midpoint impact categories	Midpoint category indicator	End-point impact Categories	End-point category indicator	Recommended level (Midpoint – End-point)	Reference
Climate change (CC) (mandatory)	Mass CO ₂ equivalent (Infrared forcing as GWP100-year)	Infectious diseases, Land loss	DALY, Extinction of species, Resource cost	I – Interim	IPCC [b-IPCC (2013)]
Ozone depletion (OD)	Mass CFC-11 equivalent (see Note 3) (UV-B radiation as Ozone Depletion Potential)	Plant damage, Skin cancer	Net primary production, DALY	I – Interim	ILCD [b-EUR 24586 EN]
Human toxicity (HTC), cancer effects	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTUh) (Concentration at human uptake level)	Cancer	DALY	II/III – II/interim	[b-EUR 24586 EN]
Human toxicity (HTNC), non-cancer effects	Comparative toxic unit for humans (CTUh) (Concentration at human uptake level)	Memory loss	DALY	II/III – Interim	[b-EUR 24586 EN]
Respiratory inorganics/Particulate matter (RI/PM)	Mass PM _{2.5} equivalent (see Note 4)	Bronchitis, Asthma attacks	DALY	II/III – II (see Note 5)	[b-EUR 24586 EN]
Ionizing radiation (IRH), human health	Mass U235 equivalent	Cancer	DALY	II – Interim	[b-EUR 24586 EN]
Ionizing radiation (IRE), ecosystems	Comparative toxic unit for ecosystems (CTUe)×volume×time			Interim – No methods recommended	
Ionizing radiation (IRE), ecosystems	Comparative toxic unit for ecosystems (CTUe)×volume×time			Interim – No methods recommended	
Eutrophication (EA), aquatic	Freshwater: Mass P-equivalents Marine water: Mass N-equivalents	Fish population	Resource cost	II – Interim	[b-EUR 24586 EN]

Table 5 – Examples of environmental impact categories and indicators

Midpoint impact categories	Midpoint category indicator	End-point impact Categories	End-point category indicator	Recommended level (Midpoint – End-point)	Reference
Eutrophication (ET), terrestrial	Mole N-equivalents	Herbivore population	Resource cost, Extinction of species	II – No methods recommended	[b-EUR 24586 EN]
Photochemical ozone formation (POF)	Mass C ₂ H ₄ -equivalents (Tropospheric O ₃ concentration increase)	Asthma, Plant damage	DALY, Net primary production	II – II	[b-EUR 24586 EN]
Acidification (A)	Mole H ⁺ -equivalent	Plant damage	Net primary production	II – Interim	[b-EUR 24586 EN]
Ecotoxicity (ETFW), freshwater (see Note 6)	Comparative toxic unit for ecosystems (CTUe)×volume×time (Concentration at aquatic ecosystem species uptake level)	Aquatic ecosystem population	Extinction of species	II/III – No methods recommended	[b-EUR 24586 EN]
Land use (LU)	Mass deficit of soil organic matter	Land loss	Extinction of species, resource cost	III – Interim	[b-EUR 24586 EN]
Resource depletion (RDW), water	Water amount as water use related to local scarcity of water	User cost	Resource cost	III – No methods recommended	[b-EUR 24586 EN]
Resource depletion (RDMR), mineral, fossil, (see Note 7)	Minerals as mass Sb-equivalent and fossil fuels as MJ (Resource amount as scarcity)	User cost	Resource cost	II – Interim	[b-EUR 24586 EN]
<p>NOTE 1 – The midpoint impact categories are suggested by the ILCD [b-EUR 24586 EN] and PEF [b-EC common methods]. For other impact categories beyond 'Climate change', the scientists are still debating on the suitable methodology and the Category indicators referred in this table may change in the future. Especially Land use methodology is still very open. Refer to ILCD and other documents for up-to-date methodology to use for each impact category.</p> <p>NOTE 2 – At the time of publication of this Recommendation, the recommended levels are taken from the most recent ILCD guideline [b-EUR 25167 EN]. Refer to ILCD guideline for the most up-to-date information and the explanation of the different recommended levels.</p> <p>NOTE 3 – CFC-11 = Trichlorofluoromethane, also called freon-11 or R-11, is a chlorofluorocarbon.</p> <p>NOTE 4 – PM_{2,5} = Particulate matter with a diameter of 2,5 µm or less.</p>					